

**THE INTERPLAY OF TEACHER EFFECTIVENESS AND LANGUAGE
INTEREST AMONG ENGLISH TEACHER EDUCATION
STUDENTS: A CONVERGENT PARALLEL STUDY**

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The Interplay of Teacher Effectiveness and Language Interest among English Teacher Education Students: A Convergent Parallel Study

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Abstract

The study examined the lived experiences and coping mechanisms of English teacher education students in relation to teacher effectiveness in maintaining language interest. Using a mixed-method design with a parallel convergent approach, the research involved 214 students for quantitative data and 14 students for qualitative in which seven participated in in-depth interviews and the other seven joined the focus group discussions. Teacher effectiveness consisted by five indicators—subject matter knowledge, instructional planning, assessment, learning environment, and communication—obtained an overall mean with a descriptive equivalent of high. Language interest with attention, motivation, enjoyment, perception, and activities as the indicators garnered a descriptive equivalent of high. Both qualitative and quantitative results converged, revealing that factors like linguistic competence, instructional mastery, and engaging environments influenced students' experiences. To sustain language interest, students used strategies such as leveraging technology, building social support, engaging with challenging materials, and managing stress. The study emphasizes the critical role of teacher effectiveness in sustaining students' language interest and recommends that educators should enhance instructional methods and create engaging learning environments.

Keywords: *teacher effectiveness, language interest, mixed methods, english teacher, education students*

Introduction

Language interest is a deep-seated curiosity and engagement with languages, their study, and their use. It involves not only the acquisition of new languages but also the exploration of linguistics and the cultural and expressive dimensions of language. This language interest plays a crucial role in learning activities, as it fosters a sustained commitment to engagement and retention without the need for external motivation. However, many students struggle with low interest in language learning, perceiving it as difficult. This perception presents a challenge for educators, who must employ a variety of creative teaching methods to ignite students' passion and engagement in language learning (Halim, 2019).

In Padangsidempuan, Indonesia, a significant challenge facing English language learners is the lack of language interest in learning, which hampers their motivation and engagement inside the classroom. Study shows that language interest often develops organically, yet many students struggle to see the relevance of English in their daily lives and academic pursuits. Moreover, this disconnection is worsened due to a curriculum that does not effectively integrate English with other subjects. Without fostering a genuine language interest in learning, through relevant and engaging contexts, students may find it difficult to navigate the complexities of language learning, leading to suboptimal educational outcomes (Ninik, 2020).

In Bataan Peninsula State University, Philippines, language interest became a significant problem in the language learning process. Students see learning a second language as essential for employment and communication, but the lack of interest leads to increased hindrance in language learning. The absence of interest to learn language results to neglecting academic advantages and non-exertion of efforts to learn the language. Further, a study suggests that diverse teaching strategies are needed to amplify students' willingness, boost their interest, and better engage in language, highlighting the importance of fostering genuine interest in the language learning process (Giray, 2022).

With these considerations in mind, this research study aims to highlight the impact of the teacher effectiveness to boosting the learners' interest in language learning. This study is rooted in the critical role language interest plays in shaping educational outcomes and cultural integration, particularly in diverse linguistic contexts. This research explores the crucial task of the teachers to the language interest of the students in English major program, offering valuable insights into their language development. Beyond the academic scope, the findings provide timely perspectives in our digitally-driven society, informing strategies for educational improvement and the comprehensive learning materials that would ignite students' language skills. The research emphasizes its importance by addressing the evolving educational aspirations and meeting the broader societal need for adaptable, effective educators in the context of language teaching-learning process.

Furthermore, there is a noticeable gap in existing research concerning the teacher effectiveness and language interest within the local academic context. While studies like Minollahi et. al (2023), entitled "Interest of the Students in the Lecturer's Teaching Performance in the Hybrid Classroom", and Kafi and Motallebzadeh (2017), entitled "Effective Teaching and Language Learning Motivation: A Study on The Interconnection". Both studies differ in terms of their focus. The first one focused on investigating students' interest in learning English for Tourism and the impact of lecturer's teaching performance on that interest, whereas the second one, focused on examining the relationship between EFL teachers' effectiveness and students' motivation levels, contributing valuable insights. While the provided published researches have explored the impact of effective teaching practices on student engagement and learning

outcomes in various subjects, including languages, there is limited empirical investigation into how teacher effectiveness influences the development and sustainability of language interest specifically among future English teachers. Addressing this gap is crucial for enhancing teacher preparation programs and optimizing educational strategies that foster both effective teaching practices and sustained student interest in language learning, particularly within the specialized domain of English language education.

This study seeks to disseminate its findings to reveal how teacher effectiveness influences language interest among English teacher education students. The dissemination strategy involves distributing hardbound copies strategically within our academic community and publishing in an esteemed international journal to ensure global reach and impact. Collaboration with the research office will facilitate a formal presentation of findings, with hardbound copies distributed to faculty and staff, fostering direct engagement and discussions. The research output will be prominently featured in the library, enhancing accessibility for students and researchers alike. Moreover, the study plans to present its findings at relevant international conferences and leverage academic and social media platforms to maximize visibility and influence within the field of language education. This version maintains the focus on the research gap related to teacher effectiveness and language interest among English teacher education students, emphasizing the dissemination strategy and potential impact of the study.

Research Questions

This study used a mixed methods approach to examine students' interest in language and teacher effectiveness by collecting and combining quantitative and qualitative data. This design leveraged the strengths of both methods to provide a more thorough understanding of the research problem.

1. What is the level of teacher effectiveness and language interest among English education students in terms of the following indicators in each variable?
2. What is the relationship of teacher effectiveness and language interest among English education students?
3. What are the lived experiences of the students relative to the effectiveness of their teachers in boosting their language interest??
4. How do students handle challenges and maintain their interest in language when teachers have varying levels of effectiveness?
6. Does the quantitative data corroborate with the qualitative data?

Methodology

Research Design

This study used a mixed methods research design in a convergent parallel approach. As defined by Johnson et al. (2017), in a single or multiphase study, mixed methods combined quantitative and qualitative methods. In order to gain a deeper understanding, it was also an investigation or approach that looks into the social world and ideally incorporates multiple methodological traditions, or ways of knowing, as well as multiple approaches to gathering, analyzing, and representing human phenomena.

This study employed a mixed method approach, incorporating both quantitative and qualitative design elements. An approved survey questionnaire was used in the quantitative phase to gauge the effectiveness of instruction and level of language interest. In the meantime, focus group discussion and in-depth interviews were used in the qualitative phase to hear participant perspectives on the noteworthy outcome of the quantitative phase.

A convergent parallel mixed method was chosen as the research design for this study. Each type of data is gathered simultaneously and given equal priority in this design. Focus group discussion or one-on-one interviews came after the survey was completed. After conducting independent analyses on the two sets of data, the results are combined and interpreted together. Given the study's objective of examining the relationships, conflicts, and convergence or divergence between the two data sources, this design is suitable (Tomasi et al., 2018).

In the context of this study, a comprehensive examination of the connection between teacher effectiveness of the teachers and language interest of the students. Both quantitative and qualitative data are gathered independently, offering a multifaceted perspective on the topic. When these data sets are merged during interpretation, a holistic understanding of how teacher effectiveness impacts language interest among English major students is achieved. This research design enables a robust analysis of the research problem and its nuanced dimensions, allowing for a more in-depth exploration of the relationship between teacher effectiveness and language interest among students.

Consequently, this research employed a descriptive-correlational approach, which involved comparing and contrasting the collected results to draw meaningful conclusions. By utilizing both quantitative and qualitative research methods, this study aimed to enhance our understanding of the teacher effectiveness and language interest among English major students and provide a foundation for effective teaching and learning strategies and techniques. Hence, the study contains both quantitative and qualitative research methods (Richardson, 2018).

In the context of this study, the descriptive-correlational approach serves as the methodological framework for my study. This approach involves systematically collecting and analyzing data to describe and understand the relationship between two key variables: teacher

effectiveness and language interest. Through descriptive statistics, it aims to provide a detailed account of the teacher effectiveness employed by teachers in the context of English language instruction.

Furthermore, the qualitative stage of this research utilized phenomenological investigation to enhance the qualitative framework. Phenomenological research aims to understand and describe the fundamental essence or significance of a specific phenomenon as experienced firsthand by individuals. Additionally, phenomenological research utilizes techniques such as extensive interviews and individual accounts to collect detailed and comprehensive descriptions, aiming to reveal the shared characteristics and interpretations that define the experience among various individual

rather than pursuing overarching assumptions (Öhlén & Friberg, 2023).

In this study's qualitative phase, the researcher used this approach to investigate the perspective of KCAST English teacher education students on teacher effectiveness and language interest, including their experiences, challenges, coping methods, and observations. Phenomenology offers a detailed and empathetic comprehension of the study by emphasizing the perspectives of participants and setting aside the researcher's preconceptions. This method enables the researcher to engage in self-reflection, aiding personal growth and enriching theory development. Therefore, conducting a thorough analysis of participant data through phenomenological inquiry enables researchers to gain a deeper understanding of the intricacies of the human experience, which cannot be fully captured using only quantitative methods.

Participants

The study focused on the English teacher education students in KCAST. This study centered on the English major students of the education department of KCAST in the local college. The students were selected as both respondents and participants of the study. Therefore, the researcher can gain understanding from various viewpoints by involving participants in examining the connection between teacher effectiveness and language interest.

Quantitative Phase

The respondents in the quantitative phase were English major students from Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology. Meanwhile, the study only included a total of 200 respondents as the research samples of the study. As explained by Budiu and Moran (2021), a total of 40 respondents is enough for a quantitative study. Also, it was added by Lamar (2022), that having 90% confidence level and 5% margin or error is accurate for quantitative research.

Lastly, Comrey and Lee (1992) highlighted that number of respondents for social research as 100 as bad, 200 as fair, 300 as good, 500 as very good, and 1000 or more as superb. Hence, having 200 respondents in the study is already enough to gather the needed data in the study as supported by these authors.

Additionally, in choosing and selecting the samples from a given population of the study, stratified random sampling was used. As explained by Simkus (2023), stratified random sampling was a method of selecting a sample in which researcher first divide a population into smaller subgroups, or strata, based on shared characteristics of the members and then randomly select among each stratum to form the final sample. In the study, the shared characteristics of the samples include their education level, degree or program, age, gender.

Lastly, in selecting and choosing the qualified respondents in the study, the researcher set an inclusion criterion as basis and guide in the selection process. This included: (1) must be enrolled in Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology; (2) must be enrolled in Institute of Teacher Education majoring in English; (3) must be currently enrolled in the previous academic year 2022-2023, second semester or in the current academic year, 2023-2024, first semester, (4) can be male or female or any gender; and (5) must have the willingness to participate in the study.

Since the study focused on the students officially enrolled in English major under the education program in KCAST, the selection of respondents was accordingly performed. Consequently, limiting the respondents to enrolled students in the English education program, with this, it was appropriate to exclude unenrolled and not English education students as respondents in the conduct of this paper.

The study was conducted among students enrolled in the Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in English program at a local college. The institution's student population in this program is composed of 104 first-year students, 64 second-year students, 32 third-year students, and 14 fourth-year students. These students were selected as the sample population for the study, ensuring a comprehensive representation across all academic levels within the program.

Table 1.1. *Distribution of Respondents*

<i>Year Level</i>	<i>Population</i>	<i>Sample</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
First Year	223	104	22.85%
Second Year	136	64	13.94%
Third Year	69	32	7.07%
Fourth Year	29	14	2.97%
Total	457	214	46.83%

Qualitative Phase

In the qualitative strand, just like the quantitative phase, the participants were teacher education students from Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology. These participants were included and involved in in-depth interview and focus-group discussions. Specifically, the study included 7 participants for the focus group discussion as well as 7 participants for In-depth interview. This conformed to the suggestion and recommendation of Creswell (2018) which pointed out that a researcher may have between 10 to 50 participants as being sufficient in qualitative research depending on the type of research and research questions.

Lastly, for the selection process, the researcher set an inclusion criterion as basis. This included: (1) enrolled students in Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology; (2) enrolled in Institute of Teacher Education majoring in English; (3) currently enrolled in the previous academic year 2022-2023, second semester or in the current academic year, 2023-2024, first semester; (4) must be a regular student; (5) can be male or female or any gender; and (6) must have the willingness to participate in the study. Since the study focused on the students officially enrolled in English major under the education program in KCAST, the selection of respondents was accordingly performed. It was appropriate to exclude unenrolled and not English education students as participant/s in the conduct of this paper.

Table 1.2. Profiles of the Participants

<i>Assigned Code</i>	<i>Year Level</i>
IDI-01	1ST year
IDI-02	2nd year
IDI-03	2nd year
IDI-04	3rd year
IDI-05	3rd year
IDI-06	3rd year
IDI-07	4th year
FGD-01	1st year
FGD-02	2nd year
FGD-03	2nd year
FGD-04	3rd year
FGD-05	3rd year
FGD-06	3rd year
FGD-07	4th year

Instrument

In this section, the research tools in gathering quantitative and qualitative data from the participants and respondents of this study were discussed.

Quantitative Phase

In identifying the level and status of teacher effectiveness as the independent variable, an adopted questionnaire from a published and conducted study was used. This questionnaire was proposed by Akram (2018). The said questionnaire had the following indicators: subject matter knowledge, instructional planning and strategies, assessment, classroom environment, and effective communication.

On the other hand, language interest as the dependent variable used an adopted and published questionnaire proposed by Nana (2011). The said questionnaire had the following variables: attention, motivation, enjoyment, perception, and activities.

Both adapted questionnaires used a five-point likert scale. The STEQ with the following descriptive level: 5 means always, 4 as often, 3 as sometimes, 2 equivalents as rarely, and 1 as never. Whereas, the language interest has the following descriptive level: 5 as very interested, 4 as interested, 3 as lack of interest, 2 as uninterested, and 1 as very uninterested.

Teacher Effectiveness. The adapted research questionnaire was used which showed high reliability and trustworthiness. The consistency of Cronbach's alpha values for each indicator suggested the instrument's internal reliability and consistency. The uniformity in the Cronbach's alpha findings among different indicators indicated that the survey reliably measured the intended constructs. The Subject Matter Knowledge had a Cronbach's alpha $\alpha = .76$, indicating to have an acceptable interpretation. Instructional Planning and Strategies obtained $\alpha = .72$; Assessment got $\alpha = .70$; Learning Environment garnered a Cronbach's alpha $\alpha = .71$; and, Effective Communication got $.70$, indicating to have an acceptable interpretation. The School Teacher Effectiveness Questionnaire or the STEQ showed a high overall reliability at $\alpha = .88$, with scale-wise reliabilities varying between $.70$ and $.76$ which indicate the Exploratory factor analysis confirmed STEQ's validity as a measure containing five factors: Subject matter knowledge, Instructional Planning and Strategies, Assessment, Classroom Environment, and Effective Communication.

Language Interest. The adapted research questionnaire demonstrated high reliability and trustworthiness, as evidenced by the consistency of Cronbach's alpha values for each indicator, which confirmed the instrument's internal reliability. The uniform Cronbach's alpha results across different indicators indicated that the survey accurately measured the intended constructs. Specifically, attention had a Cronbach's alpha of $.75$, motivation scored $.74$, enjoyment was $.80$, Learning Environment had $.77$, and Effective Communication

scored .78, all indicating acceptable reliability. This questionnaire showed high overall reliability with a Cronbach's alpha of .80, indicating the questionnaire's validity with the following identified key factors: attention, motivation, enjoyment, perception, and activities.

Qualitative Phase

In the qualitative phase, it used an interview guide which contained the grand core questions and probing and supporting questions which were used both in the in-depth interview and focus group discussions. It was validated by external validators to check the construct of the questions whether it measured what it intended to measure, or, whether it sustained the data needed in the study. In addition, in this strand, the researcher used this validated interview guide to validate the results found in the quantitative phase of the study. Lastly, the interview guide consisted of two parts. First for the letter of permission for the participants and the second one was for the interview proper.

Procedure

As the manuscript routing was completed, the researcher submitted it to the Research Office of Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology for protocol adherence and ethical clearance. After receiving approval from the Research Ethics Committee (REC), the researcher began the data collection process.

The researcher first wrote a permission letter to conduct the study, which was endorsed by the Research Office and sent to the College Presidents of Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology. Upon receiving their approval, the researcher distributed the survey questionnaire to the respondents.

Before data collection, the researcher conducted an orientation for the gatekeepers, explaining the study's nature and purpose. Informed consent forms were given to the teachers to distribute to the respondents. The researcher explained the study's goals and the respondents' roles, after which the respondents signed the consent forms, indicating their understanding and willingness to participate.

Following these preliminaries, the researcher ensured optimum confidentiality during the data gathering process, covering both qualitative and quantitative phases.

Quantitative Phase

In the quantitative phase of the study, the researcher conducted the research through face-to-face interactions. This approach involved the researcher personally distributing the survey questionnaires to the participants, ensuring direct engagement and immediate clarification if needed. To provide a clearer understanding of the data gathering process, the following steps were meticulously followed by the researcher:

First, after the respondents signed the informed consent form, they were given survey questionnaire which contained different questions for the two variables which were Teaching Effectiveness and Language Interest. In the questionnaire, the respondents were not instructed to include their name as it is optional. Also, they were given ample time to complete answering the questions so that a valid and reliable answers were provided from them;

Second, after the respondents completely answered all the stipulated questions in the survey questionnaire, the researcher and the gatekeeper completely retrieved the questionnaire in preparation for the tallying process. Consequently, the respondents were given token of appreciation as a form of gratitude in their voluntary participation in the study. Additionally, in the tallying of the responses, a format of the tallying of data was asked by the researcher to his statistician for easy treatment of the data afterwards.

Third, after tallying of the research data, the analysis and treatment of the data followed. The tallied data were given to the research statistician who was capable and was knowledgeable in data analysis and data treatment;

Fourth, when the statistician returned the result of the data analysis and treatment, the researcher analyzed and interpreted the results. Of course, this was with the help and guidance of the research adviser. This was to ensure that the analysis done was truthful and correct; and

Here's an expanded version of your text:

Lastly, throughout the entire process of data gathering, as well as during the subsequent stages of data treatment, analysis, and interpretation, strict measures were implemented to ensure the confidentiality of the information obtained from the research respondents. To safeguard the data, all completed survey questionnaires were securely stored in a locked box. This security measure ensured that only the researcher had access to the collected data. These precautions guaranteed that no unauthorized individuals could access or tamper with the gathered information, thereby maintaining the integrity and confidentiality of the research findings.

Qualitative Phase

In the qualitative phase, one-on-one interviews were conducted with identified participants to gather their lived experiences and insights on teacher effectiveness and language interest. A structured interview guide was used for these in-depth interviews. The researcher followed these procedures:

First, with informed consent already obtained from the respondents, the researcher selected 14 participants for in-depth interviews and focus group discussions, with the gatekeeper's help in identifying qualified participants based on set criteria.

Second, an orientation for the 14 selected participants was conducted to inform them about their roles in the next research stage. Participants were allowed to withdraw, and if needed, new participants were recruited by the gatekeeper and researcher.

Third, the researcher conducted face-to-face one-on-one interviews with seven participants, followed by focus group discussions with the remaining seven participants, ensuring convenience for all.

Fourth, the researcher transcribed all individual responses verbatim and prepared separate transcripts for the focus group discussion.

Fifth, participants were given copies of their transcripts to verify accuracy. They could request changes or additions, which the researcher accommodated.

Lastly, once transcripts were verified, the researcher proceeded with thematic analysis of the data.

Data Analysis

Data analysis involved gathering, organizing, changing, explaining, modeling, and understanding data to uncover valuable insights and aid decision-making. Listed were the important stages including gathering data, analyzing data, converting data, and understanding and displaying outcomes. The researcher made sure that the data was precise, thorough, and reflective of the issue under investigation.

Quantitative Phase

In here, descriptive statistics, like the average and total of the collected data, were used in quantitative data analysis to assess the level of each variable's indicators, dividing them by the total number of data points. Additionally, the Pearson correlation coefficient (r) was employed to examine the connection between teacher effectiveness and language interest among English teacher education students in KCAST. Kenton (2022) stated that the Pearson correlation coefficient is commonly utilized across different fields for evaluating the strength of the association and measuring the linear relationship between two variables. It is crucial to recognize that a strong correlation does not automatically indicate causation, since there could be other variables impacting the relationship. Conversely, the survey data that was gathered formed the foundation for detailed investigation. After collecting the questionnaires, the data was compiled and processed as needed. The survey data was additionally examined with Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) for descriptive-correlation statistics. These statistical methods were used to determine the situation of English teacher education students in the local college.

Qualitative Phase

The researcher used a thorough qualitative data analysis method, incorporating coding and thematic analysis techniques to systematically analyze the patterns and themes found in the participants' spoken responses during individual interviews. The coding procedure involved meticulously categorizing and arranging the qualitative data into distinct codes that reflected the fundamental themes, notions, and thoughts in the original data, employing both inductive and deductive approaches (Medelyan, 2024).

Expanding on the coding phase, the researcher proceeded with thematic analysis to uncover overarching themes that amalgamated various codes, highlighting the intricate meanings, importance, and connections within the data, aiming to examine how teacher effectiveness relates to the language interest among English teacher education students. The information was thoroughly examined to identify the most important themes, offering valuable insights into the research goals and participants' experiences, perceptions, and perspectives in the educational setting. Furthermore, it enabled the researcher to make valuable inferences from the qualitative data, improving the thoroughness and excellence of the research results.

Ethical Considerations

The study was conducted responsibly and respectfully, using both qualitative and quantitative approaches, with a strong emphasis on safeguarding the rights and well-being of participants (Mack et al., 2005). To uphold these ethical standards, various measures were implemented throughout the mixed-method research. The study followed the ethical principles outlined in the International Ethical Guidelines for Health-Related Research Involving Humans (2016), which include considerations such as social value, informed consent, protection of vulnerable participants, justice, transparency, researcher qualifications, adequacy of facilities, community involvement, risk-benefit balance, safety, privacy, and confidentiality. Prior to commencing the study, the Research Ethics Committee thoroughly reviewed and validated the manuscript multiple times to ensure compliance with these ethical guidelines.

In order to uphold the trust of the mathematics teacher education students from KCAST, the study prioritized their safety, anonymity, complete protection, and confidentiality as key concerns. Measures were taken to ensure that these ethical considerations were carefully addressed, aiming to maintain the trust of the participants throughout the course of the study.

Social Value. The study investigates the social challenges and experiences faced by the English teacher education program with regards to teacher effectiveness and language interest. Through examining these factors, the researcher aims to identify barriers that may hinder the development of proficient English educators and to propose strategies that can enhance both teaching efficacy and student

engagement. The findings have the potential to contribute significantly to improving educational outcomes by addressing the underlying social dynamics that influence teacher performance and language enthusiasm in educational settings.

Moreover, the researcher of the study comprehensively explained the overall procedure needed in order to get the full participation of English teacher education students, particularly to the main purpose of the study as well as the procedure in data collection. Hence, the results of the study were shown for them and disseminated to other possible audiences who could benefit from the study. More importantly, the researcher adhered to social value in research by being truthfully committed to the rigor of convergent parallel mixed method design as utilized in the study.

Informed Consent. To ensure the ethical conduct of the study, the researcher of the study provided the participants with letters of permission and consent in both qualitative and quantitative that outlined the details of the study, including the methods, design, and procedures. These letters were intended to help the participants understand the nature of the study and made informed decisions about whether to participate. Participants who did not decide to participate are allowed to leave without any explanations and assured that their data remained confidential. By following these ethical guidelines, the researcher ensured that the study was conducted in a responsible and respectful manner.

Vulnerability of the Research Participants. The research of the study was fully taken into consideration the vulnerability of the participants. Further, the conduction of both qualitative and quantitative data was fully addressed with consents stipulated with their signature that signifies that they agreed to participate in the data gathering hence, English teacher education students were less vulnerable from the study. Additionally, the interview as well as the dissemination of survey questionnaires were given specific schedules based upon the convenience of the participants. Lastly, participants were given tokens for their efforts in the participation to succeed the study.

The Risks, Benefits and Safety. As an ethical principle, the researcher emphasizes the commitment to minimize risks and maximize the well-being of research participants. In this study, efforts made to ensure the safety and protection of the participants. Anonymity of the interviewees maintained to prevent any potential risks to their privacy and confidentiality. All files of information were properly secured and not left unattended or unprotected. Additionally, the data gathered during this research study was exclusively utilized for the specified research objectives. The study's outcomes may also be disseminated through various means, including presentations within the institution, publication in scientific forums or journals, and presentations at conferences, whether on a local, national, or international scale. The researcher's intent in sharing the study's findings contributed to the broader body of knowledge within their field of study.

Privacy and Confidentiality of Information. Towards the data, results and findings including the safeguard of participants, different techniques were used. Conversely, all personal identities of the participants were hidden and not shown including audio records, encoded transcripts, notes, soft and hard copies of data and others should be eliminated right after the data is analyzed. Further, to protect the participant's identity and ensure compliance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012, the researcher used discrete coding to denote each participant's responses. This measure involved carefully phrasing any information that could potentially identify the participants in terms of their name, gender, ethnicity, or employment/location to avoid violating their anonymity. By using proper coding and other measures, the researcher was able to protect the participant's identity and ensure that their privacy was respected.

Justice. In this study, the researcher ensured the rights of the participants who identified themselves as English teacher education students. Given that the study aimed to explore the interplay of teacher effectiveness and language interest among English teacher education, no rights of minors were violated. In recognition of their contribution, they were duly credited for their involvement in the research, contributing to the overall success of the study. To ensure fairness and equal opportunity for participation, the researcher utilized random sampling and purposive sampling techniques. Additionally, board programs instructors are not coerced into participating and were given the freedom to decline if they so choose. In recognition of their contribution, tokens were provided to the participants, and duly credited for their involvement in the research, contributing to the overall success of the study. Also, justice was ensured by including only relevant utterances of the participants related to the research objectives and accurately transcribing them.

Transparency. The study adhered to the principles of transparency as the researcher fully informed the participants to be aware that the study is solely focusing to the experiences and challenges of the English teacher education students with regards to teacher effectiveness and language interest. Moreover, the researcher did not have any connection regarding to the identified participants since, the study is purposively sampling and only identified instructors under English education students were being selected without subjectivity and biases regarding to their statuses. Further, the interview notes and transcribed notes were presented to the participants for their confirmation and approval. The results were also shared to the participants by the researcher.

Qualifications of the Researcher. The research of the study was credible to undertake the study of mixed design about the interplay of teacher effectiveness and language interest among English teacher education students, as the researcher is a third-year student of Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in English and were enrolled from the course Language Research 2 in fulfillment for the requirement. Furthermore, the study had undergone multiple validations which was started from the researchers' adviser up to the panelists making sure that it is appropriate and has the standard from the principles of thesis writing. Also, the interpretation of the statistical data was credible as the researcher had undergone Statistics subject. Lastly, the choice of the municipality as well as the

college institution where the English teacher education students was justified as the researcher is currently leaving on the nearby municipality.

Adequacy of Facilities. The adequacy of facilities addressed by the researcher since, the study only utilized resources that are already available such as the bond papers for the questionnaires, cellphone for the audio and tracking of the responses, as well as the laptop and printer which was the primary facility to succeed the study. Further, the source of funds was supported by the parents of the researcher, including the resources to be used in disseminating survey questionnaires for the quantitative part, tokens and snacks for the interviewees in the qualitative part, also the research fee which attained a significant amount to undergone the outline defense and final-defense. Thus, after gathering the significant data for the, the researcher directly consulted to the data analyst for guiding corrections and improvements for the themes. Further, the researcher consulted also to the certified statistician for the correct interpretation of the data. Hence, these things were undergone to avoid any delay to come up with immediate result and complete the required publication from the institution.

Community Involvement. The study involved a community of English teacher education students by which, it is the solely focused of the study and should be presented. These students had come across with their experiences and challenges with regards to the teacher effectiveness and language interest. Further, the results may gather insights for the future endeavors making it as their instrument in grasping knowledge and solving problems in the field from this study. Lastly, the beneficiaries of the study were part of the community where in the college institution, where also the study was conducted.

Results and Discussion

Status of Teacher Effectiveness and Language Interest among English Teacher Education Students in Local College

The results of the survey of the two variables namely: teacher effectiveness and language interest, are presented here. Moreover, the overall mean, including the items with the highest and the lowest ratings per indicator were given.

Status of Teacher Effectiveness

Shown in the Table 2.1 is the response of English teacher education students in the local college. It obtained an overall mean score of 4.21 with a descriptive equivalent as high. This means that the English education students oftentimes manifested the teacher effectiveness. The variable of the study which is teacher effectiveness has five indicators namely: subject matter knowledge, instructional planning strategies, assessment, learning environment, and effective communications.

Subject Matter Knowledge. In terms of subject matter knowledge, the category mean is 4.17 with a descriptive equivalent as high. This means that it is oftentimes manifested by English teacher education students in the local college. Among the items under this indicator, item number 5 - relating the content to real-life situations by making the lessons more relevant and applicable to our daily lives got the highest mean of 4.22 with a descriptive equivalent as high. This means that it is oftentimes manifested by the students. On the other hand, the lowest item rated by the respondents was the item number 3 - using diverse teaching methods by keeping the lessons engaging and catering to different learning styles of the students and has a mean of 4.14 with a descriptive equivalent as high. This means that it is oftentimes manifested by the English teacher education students.

Table 2.1. *Status of Teacher Effectiveness*

<i>Variables and Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
A. Subject Matter Knowledge		
1. Showing a strong grasp of the subject matter by making lessons clear and informative.	4.16	High
2. Connecting current topics to previous and upcoming lessons to help us understand the material better.	4.15	High
3. Using diverse teaching methods by keeping the lessons engaging and catering to different learning styles of the students.	4.14	High
4. Presenting subject matter in a way that is easy for me to understand and access.	4.18	High
5. Relating the content to real-life situations by making the lessons more relevant and applicable to our daily lives.	4.22	High
Category Mean	4.17	High
B. Instructional Planning and Strategies		
Using different teaching strategies to enhance students' understanding.	4.22	High
1. Changing teaching methodology to make topics relevant to students' lives.	4.07	High
2. Teaching the students according to their individual differences.	4.04	High
3. Using appropriate material, technology and resources while teaching.	4.29	Very High
4. Engaging, motivating, and maintaining students' attention to their lesson.	4.31	Very High
Category Mean	4.19	High
C. Assessment		
1. Conducting class tests to monitor students' performance regularly.	4.06	High
2. Evaluating students' performance and provide timely feedback on their errors.	4.04	High
3. Maintaining a record of students' results.	4.18	High
4. Using multiple assessment strategies.	4.10	High

5. Encouraging students to do better next time.	4.33	Very High
Category Mean	4.14	High
D. Learning Environment		
1. Creating a climate of mutual trust and respect in the classroom.	4.23	High
2. Emphasizing continuous improvement towards students' achievement.	4.29	Very High
3. Maintaining a classroom setting that minimizes disruption.	4.07	High
4. Creating an attractive and friendly classroom environment.	4.32	Very High
5. Ensuring students' participation in the learning process.	4.38	Very High
Category Mean	4.26	Very High
E. Effective Communications		
1. Using correct vocabulary and grammar in teaching.	4.34	Very High
2. Explaining lessons according to the age and ability of the students.	4.12	High
3. Responding to students' questions in appropriate language.	4.36	Very High
4. Making myself open for opinions and suggestions from the students about my mistakes of the grammar use.	4.38	Very High
5. Listening students' perspectives about their struggles with learning.	4.27	Very High
Category Mean	4.29	Very High
Overall Mean	4.21	High

Instructional Planning and Strategies. The instructional planning and strategies were rated by the respondents with a descriptive equivalent as high with a category mean score of 4.19. This means that it is oftentimes manifested by the English teacher education students. Item number 5 - engaging, motivating, and maintaining students' attention to their lesson obtained the highest rating of 4.31 with a descriptive equivalent as very high and is always manifested by the students. Conversely, item number 3 - teaching the students according to their individual differences got the lowest mean of 4.04 with a descriptive equivalent as high and is oftentimes manifested by the English teacher education students.

Assessment. The assessment garnered a mean score of 4.14 with a descriptive equivalent as high which means that it is oftentimes manifested by the students. Item number 5 - encouraging students to do better next time got the highest mean score of 4.33 with a descriptive equivalent as very high which means that it is always manifested by the English teacher education students. On the other hand, item number 2 - evaluating students' performance and provide timely feedback on their errors obtained the lowest mean of 4.04 with a descriptive equivalent as high which means that it is oftentimes manifested by the students.

Learning Environment. The learning environment got a mean score of 4.26 with a descriptive equivalent as very high which means that it is always manifested by the students. Item number 5 - ensuring students' participation in the learning process received the highest rate from the respondents of 4.38 mean score with a descriptive equivalent as very high which means that it is always manifested by the English teacher education students. Item number 3 - maintaining a classroom setting that minimizes disruption, on the other hand got the lowest rate of 4.07 mean score with a descriptive equivalent as high which means it is oftentimes manifested by the students.

Effective Communications. The effective communications obtained a mean score of 4.29 with a descriptive equivalent as very high which means that it is always manifested by the students. Item number 4 - making myself open for opinions and suggestions from the students about my mistakes of the grammar use got the highest mean score of 4.38 with a descriptive equivalent as very high which means that it is always manifested by the English teacher education students. On the other hand, item number 2 - explaining lessons according to the age and ability of the students got the lowest rate of 4.12 mean score with a descriptive equivalent as high which means that it is oftentimes manifested by the students.

Status of Language Interest

Displayed on the Table 2.2 are the responses from the English teacher education students in the local college. It garnered an overall rate of 4.09 mean score with a descriptive equivalent as high which means that it is oftentimes manifested by the English teacher education students in the local college. The variable of the study which is the Language Interest has five indicators namely: attention, motivation, enjoyment, perception, and activities.

Table 2.2. Status of Language Interest

<i>Variables and Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
A. Attention		
1. Giving my whole attention in learning English.	4.27	Very High
2. Learning English comfortably at home.	4.00	High
3. Spending time crafting materials about English-related topics.	3.95	High
4. Doing English tasks given by my teacher with attention focused in doing it.	4.25	High
5. Reading educational materials in English for comprehensive understanding.	4.15	High
Category Mean	4.13	High
B. Motivation		
1. Practicing a daily habit of reading English books to enhance language proficiency.	4.06	High
2. Utilizing social media platforms as a means to learn and practice English.	4.13	High

3.	Engaging in daily English conversations to facilitate a smoother and quicker language acquisition process.	4.94	High
4.	Pursuing English language skills for academic and subjects' grade improvement.	4.14	High
5.	Exerting significant effort and dedication in completing English course to ensure a better understanding of the material.	4.29	Very High
	Category Mean	4.11	Very High
C. Enjoyment			
1.	Enjoying learning English during my free time.	3.92	High
2.	Asking my friends happily about their favorite English literature.	3.73	High
3.	Engaging myself with English materials.	4.16	High
4.	Feeling fulfilled when reading English short stories and poems.	4.07	High
5.	Learning English as it gives me chills even if it is a bit difficult to deal with.	3.89	High
	Category Mean	3.95	High
D. Perception			
1.	Learning English despite its difficulty for numerous opportunities.	4.08	Very High
2.	Seeking ways to learn English to achieve my goals.	4.20	Very High
3.	Attending English language lectures for additional learning.	4.04	Very High
4.	Building bonds with fluent English speakers to be influenced and improve my language skill.	3.99	Very High
5.	Sacrificing free time solely for English language learning.	3.97	High
	Category Mean	4.06	Very High
E. Activities			
1.	Listening to the class when the teacher uses methods of singing to improve our English speaking skills.	4.18	High
2.	Engaging in class activities involving English-related games instructed by the teacher.	4.06	High
3.	Acquiring English skills through collaborative group activities.	4.16	High
4.	Enhancing my English proficiency by watching movies.	4.36	Very High
5.	Practicing language skills through role-playing when English is used.	4.17	High
	Category Mean	4.19	High
	Overall Mean	4.09	High

Attention. Attention as an indicator obtained a rate of 4.13 mean score with a descriptive equivalent as high which means that it is oftentimes manifested by the students. Item number 1 - giving my whole attention in learning English got the highest mean score of 4.27 with a descriptive equivalent as very high which means that it is always manifested by the English education students. Conversely, item number 3 - spending time crafting materials about English-related topics got the lowest rate of 3.95 mean score described as high which means that it is oftentimes manifested by the mentioned students.

Motivation. The motivation garnered a rate of 4.11 mean score with a descriptive equivalent as high which means that it is oftentimes manifested by the English teacher education students in the local college. Item number 5 - exerting significant effort and dedication in completing English course to ensure a better understanding of the material got the highest mean score of 4.29 with a descriptive equivalent as very high which means that it is always manifested by the students.

On the other hand, item number 3 - engaging in daily English conversations to facilitate a smoother and quicker language acquisition process obtained the lowest rate of 3.94 mean score with a descriptive equivalent as high which means that it is oftentimes manifested by the English teacher education students.

Enjoyment. The enjoyment obtained a rate of 3.95 mean score with a descriptive equivalent as high which means that it is oftentimes manifested by the students. Item number 3 - engaging myself with English materials got the highest rate of 4.16 mean score with a descriptive equivalent as high which means that it is oftentimes manifested by English teacher educations students. Item number 2 - asking my friends happily about their favorite English literature, on the other hand, got the lowest rate of 3.73 mean score with a descriptive equivalent as high which means that it is oftentimes manifested by the students.

Perception. The perception garnered a rate of 4.06 mean score with a descriptive equivalent as high which means that it is oftentimes manifested by the students. Item number 2 - seeking ways to learn English to achieve my goals got the highest rate of 4.20 mean score with a descriptive equivalent as high which means that it is oftentimes manifested by the students in the local college. On the other hand, item number 5 - sacrificing free time solely for English language learning got the lowest mean score of 3.97 with a descriptive equivalent as high which means that it is oftentimes manifested by the mentioned students.

Activities. The activities obtained a rate of 4.19 mean score with a descriptive equivalent as high which means that it is oftentimes manifested by the English teacher education students. Item number 4 - enhancing my English proficiency by watching movies garnered the highest rate of 4.36 with a descriptive equivalent as very high which means that it is always manifested by the students.

Whereas, item number 2 - engaging in class activities involving English-related games instructed by the teacher got the lowest rate of 4.06 mean score with a descriptive equivalent as high which means that it is oftentimes manifested, indicating that students are slightly less frequently engaged in compared to other methods, such as watching movies.

Significant Relationship between Teacher Effectiveness and Language Interest among English Teacher Education Students

Table 2 presented the results of the specific correlation analysis between the relationship of teacher effectiveness and language interest among the English teacher education students. A thorough examination of the data revealed that the teacher effectiveness (M=4.21) and language interest (M=4.09) have low positive correlation, as per the description of Cohen and Holliday (1983) on the range of different levels of correlation.

The results reflected in the table show a significant relationship between Teacher Effectiveness and Language Interest. Pearson r illustrates the relationship of teacher effectiveness and language interest. The researcher was measuring two parameters in this study, since the researcher estimates two relationships, the degree of freedom corresponds to the sample size (214) minus 2. Therefore, the $r(212) = .348$ indicates a moderately strong positive linear relationship between the two variables. This means that as one variable increases, the other variable also increases, but the relationship is not perfect. The closer the value to 1, the stronger the linear relationship between variables. This can be interpreted that there is a total of 34% of the variance of teacher effectiveness and language interest, and the remaining 66% is due to other variables not covered in the study. Meanwhile, the probability value ($p < .001$) is less than the level of significance at 0.05. Since the p-value is less than the chosen significance level of 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected, supporting the conclusion that there is a significant relationship between teacher effectiveness and language interest.

Table 3.1. Significant Relationship Between Teacher Effectiveness and Language Interest among English Teacher Education Students

Variable	Mean	R-Value	P-Value	Decision @ =0.05
Teacher Effectiveness	4.21			
Language Interest	4.09	.348	<.001	Ho Rejected

The Lived Experiences of the English Major Students Relative to the Effectiveness of Their Teachers in boosting Their Language Interest

Six essential themes were derived from in-depth interviews and focus group discussions conducted with participants in response to the first research question. Before presenting the findings, profiles of participants for the qualitative data collection were provided in Table 3.1. This table presented the profiles of participants selected purposively, meeting inclusion criteria of being a 1st year, 2nd year, 3rd year, and 4th year English major education students in KCAST. The profiles were categorized based on participants' year level.

Additionally, Table 3.2 explored the lived experiences of English teacher education students regarding teacher effectiveness and language interest. The table presented essential themes derived from transcriptions of participants' responses to research question number one. These themes encompass overarching concepts summarized within the table.

Table 3.2. Lived Experiences of the Students Relative to the Effectiveness of Teachers in Boosting their Language Interest

Probed Issues	Core Ideas	Code/ Category	Essential Theme	Theoretical Perspectives
Specific Challenges encountered in Language Learning Journey	Having difficulty in absorbing the meaning of unfamiliar	Lack of Vocabulary Skills	Linguistic and Discourse Competence Issues	Cognitive Linguistics and Schema Theories
	Finding it hard to understand the instructors' highfalutin or specialized terms			
	Struggling to understand the teacher's usage of highfalutin words, which intimidates language learning			
	Expressing oneself with disorganized words due to lack of vocabulary	Comprehension Problem on Linguistic Concepts		
	Having limited vocabulary and difficulty retaining words due to lack of use at home			
	Having difficulty grasping English concepts and language learning theories			
	Being not able to grasp concepts in English lessons like universal grammar			
	Struggling with memorizing, using, and applying grammar rules	Speaking Proficiency Challenge		
	Lacking proficiency in speaking especially in explaining English concepts			
	Being not fluent in speaking English			
Having pronunciation issues	Restrained Language Learning Method	External and Internal Factors in Language Learning	Sociocultural Theory	
Stuttering when talking				
Deeming scarcity of English learning materials as a challenge				
Lacking exposure to authentic language use				

	<p>Having problem on the availability of teachers teaching effectively</p> <p>Lacking hands-on English teachers results in a shallow understanding of literature and grammar</p> <p>Transitioning to blended learning hinders meaningful language learning</p> <p>Becoming pressured on the teacher's expectation in speaking English fluently</p> <p>Being anxious in speaking in fear of committing mistakes in grammar</p> <p>Having anxiety on using English in school in fear of being judged by English major classmates</p> <p>Being introvert person</p> <p>Having no passion in public communication lacking self-esteem</p>	<p>Lack of Teaching Competence</p> <p>School System Restructuring</p> <p>Psychological Issues</p> <p>Personality Traits</p>		
<p>Contribution of Teachers in Hurdling Language Learning Challenges</p>	<p>Giving guidance on sentence construction techniques</p> <p>Providing clear explanations</p> <p>Explaining the concept or highfalutin word</p> <p>Acting as a foundation for acquiring language knowledge and skills</p> <p>Guiding and transmitting knowledge to understand lessons</p> <p>Becoming proficient in the language, as one cannot teach what they do not know.</p> <p>Employing strategies like "last man standing" during oral recitation</p> <p>Offering reading materials to create opportunities for practice like peer-interaction</p> <p>Serving as guide by offering scaffolding to have an effective language learning journey</p> <p>Devising a rule which requires utilization of English in the class</p> <p>Having activities like conversation or dialogue in English</p> <p>Giving of authentic activities such as role play with constructive feedbacking</p> <p>Employing group-based and delegated tasks to promote cooperation and learning</p> <p>Incorporating interactive activities allowing everyone to feel inclusion</p>	<p>Clear Language Instruction</p> <p>Transfer of Knowledge and Learning</p> <p>Teaching Strategies</p> <p>Interactive Group-based activity</p>	<p>Mastery in Instructional and Content Delivery</p>	<p>Pedagogical Content Knowledge and Constructivist Theories</p>
<p>Instances signifying the impact of teachers on interest and engagement in language studies</p>	<p>Manifesting a positive learning environment by being open to questions and clarifications.</p> <p>Recognizing students' answers</p> <p>Creating an environment for using English without fear of judgment for grammar mistakes</p> <p>Creating a good and positive environment thru giving feedback in a friendly manner</p> <p>Incorporating real-world examples and cultural insights</p> <p>Focusing in the application of language in real-life situations</p> <p>Using real-life situations to connect lessons to everyday living</p>	<p>Positive Learning Climate</p> <p>Real-life Language Application</p>	<p>Engaging and Vibrant Learning Environment</p>	<p>Task-based Language Teaching Theory and Self-determination Theory</p>
<p>Effective teaching methods or activities in fostering interest in language</p>	<p>Role playing to assess confidence in character portrayal</p> <p>Having a dialogue between students and teachers</p> <p>Using language by conversing or communicating with someone in English</p>	<p>Role-playing and Dialogue</p>	<p>Group Speaking Activities</p>	<p>Sociocultural Theory</p>

Contribution of teachers in addressing challenges in language learning	Having group discussions like brainstorming with classmates	Group discussion		
	Having group discussions within group members			
	Incorporating debate, extemporaneous speaking	Speaking Tasks or Activities		
	Engaging into impromptu speaking			
	Using readers theatre as assessment for vocabulary skills			
	Ensuring one's expertise in language teaching	Pedagogical Knowledge	Teacher's Teaching Competence	Cognitive Load, TPACK Framework, Assessment for Learning Theories
	Serving as inspiration to enhance language skills thru their competence			
	Being equipped and have mastery in teaching			
	Using technology to assess English skills through simulations	Technology Integration		
	Integrating technology in instruction for 21st century learners			
Assessing and evaluating to identify areas for improvement	Assessment and Evaluation			
Identifying students' strengths and weaknesses for language feedback				

Linguistic and Discourse Competence Issues. In the context of teacher effectiveness and language interest, some experiences experienced by the students are Lack of Vocabulary Skills, Comprehension Problem on Linguistic Concepts, and Speaking Proficiency Challenge. It was mentioned by the participants that having experienced these challenges have impacted their learning in language.

Lack of Vocabulary Skills. This is the first code of the first probed issue. Students expressed common responses about having this challenge that gives them difficulty in language learning. Most of the participants responded that they are greatly challenged in using the language because of lacking vast vocabulary of words that affect their comprehension in learning materials in English.

Similarly, Participant 1 recognized that lacking vocabulary skills is a problem in language learning. Having difficulties in absorbing the meaning of unfamiliar words affects negatively the language learning process of the participant. This could greatly impact the process of learning a language as it hinders learners to comprehend and accurately grasp the exact meaning of words. He stated that:

“In terms of absorbing the words one of the difficulty and challenges that I encountered is the meanings so what are the true meaning of those words.” (IDI-01)

(When it comes to understanding words, one of the difficulties and challenges I have encountered is figuring out their meanings. I often struggle to grasp the true meanings of those words.)

Furthermore, Participant 4 elaborated on the impact of encountering highfalutin words and specialized terms on his comprehension and idea generation. He explained that such language barrier hinders his ability to engage in English conversations and discussions effectively. The complexity of vocabulary presents a significant problem to the language learning journey of the learners as they become hesitant to speak up and use the language in having conversations, afraid to misunderstand the meaning of a certain word. As what the participant said:

“Kana gong mga highfalutin words. Amoang mga instructors, expert jud when it comes to English, so, they use highfalutin words nga kanang dili gyud ko kasabot, dili lang pud akong mga instructor but as well as ako pong mga classmates, sir, so ginaconsider nako sya nga challenges nga akong naencounter sa akong language learning journey.” (IDI-04)

(When it comes to those highfalutin words, our instructors are really experts in English, so they often use those sophisticated words that I really do not understand, sir. It is not just my instructors, but also my classmates who face the same challenge. So, I consider it as one of the challenges I have encountered in my language learning journey.)

In addition, Participant 5 concurred, noting that the difficulty in grasping the meaning of unfamiliar words or encountering highfalutin and specialized terms significantly hampers his language learning journey. He emphasized that these challenges create barriers to understanding and retention, making it harder to progress, leading to frustration and lessens his confidence in his language abilities, a factor that negatively affects an individual's language learning. He stated that:

“I've actually encountered a lot of challenges in learning the language that I am right now, which is English, but specifically I would say na I've been struggling to understand, most especially if teachers tend to use like highfalutin words.” (IDI-05)

(I have faced numerous challenges in learning the language I am currently studying, which is English. Specifically, I find it difficult to understand, especially when teachers use sophisticated vocabulary.)

Furthermore, Participant 6 shared his struggles with understanding the teacher's usage of highfalutin words, which he finds intimidating

in his language learning process. He considers this a significant factor that reduces his engagement and use of English. The complex vocabulary creates a barrier to comprehension, leading to feelings of intimidation and reluctance to participate. He stated that:

“Kanang mang—mag ask og question amoang instructor is we speak in English jud ba like fluent gud like ang expectations sa instructor ba kay dapat ma-meet gud. Like ma pressure man gud mi mga students like ana gud.” (IDI-06)

(When times that our instructor asks us and they expect us to speak English fluently and meet their expectations. It can be quite pressuring for us as students.)

Moreover, expressing oneself with disorganized words due to lack of vocabulary as a difficulty can arise in various situations, affecting both personal and professional communication. Individuals experiencing this challenge may feel frustrated and insecure, may not be able to fully express their thoughts and ideas about a certain concept. This problem undoubtedly seen as a factor that lessens learners’ eagerness to take part and participate in a certain communicative context. As what

Participant 7 stated that:

“mahadlok ko na mag speak og English kay basin naa koy mamali og kanang—mamali akong grammar, and also is, kanang usahay, maglagot pud ko pag the way ko mag estorya is makuan ko kanang makambyo kambyo nako ang kanang words nga dili pa kaayo nako hasa og vocabulary sakong first year jud ana gani ko nga ‘tama kaya akong gigamit nga words.” (IDI-07)

(I am afraid to speak in English because I might make mistakes. My grammar might be wrong, and also, sometimes I get frustrated with the way I tell stories. I struggle with changing the words that I am not very familiar with, especially given my limited vocabulary from my first year. That is why I wonder if the words I use are correct.)

Furthermore, having limited vocabulary, and inability to use correct words and having a problem on retaining vocabulary as it will not be used at home is also a factor that impedes the learning process. The rarity of usage with the language lessly uphold retention and effective learning as learners are not constantly exposed nor directly using the language. With this, there would be tendencies that learners are ineffectively learning the language and may have difficulties in using the language. FGD-01 stated:

“Uhhmm challenges in language learning include difficulty grasping grammar concept, and also pronunciation issues and lack of exposure to authentic language use kay given the fact that I was raised in a family of which the language is different from my—my native language is different from English, so, that is why I am having a difficulty in using the language itself which is English.” (FGD-01)

(Challenges in language learning include difficulty grasping grammar concepts, pronunciation issues, and a lack of exposure to authentic language use. I was raised in a family where a different language is spoken, so my native language is not English. This is why I am having difficulty using the English language.)

Comprehension Problem on Linguistic Concepts. The second code from the first probed issue pertains to difficulties in understanding educational concepts, particularly those related to linguistics. Participants in both individual in-depth interviews (IDI) and focus group discussions (FGD) expressed struggles in grasping linguistic-related topics within the realm of education. These challenges with comprehension create significant hurdles for them.

In that sense, having problem on grasping different English concepts, scopes and language learning theories and its underlying explanations were seen as a challenge for the participants in engaging themselves to language learning, giving them hard time in unravelling concepts having underlying meanings or deeper ideas. Similarly, Participant 2 said that:

“Specific challenges so far, the most challenging journey I have faced in language learning is grasping different concepts, incorporating what English language is, and what are its scopes. So, mainly, the concepts po. In specific sense po talaga, for example, different theories under English language specifically kay English man gyud atong ginatun’an. So, that’s one, theories and the underlying explanations that each theorist, for example, ila Chomsky, and those persons po.” (IDI-02)

(The most challenging aspect of my language learning journey has been grasping various concepts, incorporating what the English language entails, and understanding its scopes. Mainly, it is about the concepts, specifically different theories within the English language. For example, we primarily study English, focusing on theories and the underlying explanations by each theorist, such as Chomsky and other individuals.)

Moreover, Participant 4 stated that being not able to grasp concepts in English lessons is undeniably a great challenge for them. This difficulty not only affects their immediate understanding but also hampers their overall academic progress and confidence. It reflects broader issues in language proficiency and access to resources within the education system. She stated that:

“kana ganing the topics itself, sa English usahay kay dili ko kasabot, like lisod jud kaayo sya sabton, so, I think, mao pud na sya challenge sakoa nga kana ganing ang mga topics nga dili ko kasabot sa ilang kana ganing like sa mga concept gud pareha atong mga universal grammar, so, para sakoa kay lisod kaayo sya e-grasp gud so, gina consider pud nako sya nga challenge.” (IDI-04)

(Regarding the topics themselves in English, sometimes I find it really difficult to comprehend them. This is also a challenge for me—

understanding complex concepts like universal grammar. These topics are hard for me to grasp, so I consider that a significant challenge as well.)

Additionally, as shared by FGD-03, being perplexed in memorizing, using, and applying rules having difficulty grasping grammar concept. This challenge extends beyond mere memorization, involving complexities in understanding language structure and syntax. The dynamic nature of language, coupled with contextual nuances, adds to their frustration and disillusionment. She stated that:

“Ang sa akong pud nga case nu kay, diba, if mag learn ta og kanang language kay daghan—daghan kaayo og rules gani kanang mga rules nga need e-memorize to the point nga maglibog na gani ko sa kanang unsa nga rules ang iapply sa us—sa kana nga—unsaon pag form ana nga sentence. Mao na akoang biggest jud nga problem when it com—ay biggest na challenge nu nga akong na encounter.” (FGD-03)

(In my case as well, when learning a language, there are so many rules that need to be memorized. I often get confused about which rules to apply when forming a sentence. That is really my biggest problem, or rather, my biggest challenge that I have encountered.)

Speaking Proficiency Challenge. This is the third code in the first probed issue of which participants responded to be having difficulty in language learning. The speaking proficiency challenge encompasses a variety of hurdles faced by the participants striving to communicate effectively in a particular language, often English. This challenge manifests in several ways, including struggles with articulation, coherence, and fluency. Encountering this challenge makes it difficult for them to express clearly their idea, leading to misunderstandings and frustration.

With this, lacking proficiency in speaking, particularly in explaining English concepts, is a significant barrier to effective communication and comprehension. This difficulty challenge encountered by the participant extends beyond mere fluency and encompasses the inability to articulate complex ideas and concepts in a clear and coherent manner. As stated by Participant 2:

“So, dili ko ing’ana gyud ka proficient in terms of talking or speaking the language, anytime or anywhere, so, awkward sa usahay sa akong mga magspeak.” (IDI-02)

(So, I’m not really that proficient in terms of talking or speaking the language, anytime or anywhere, so, it’s sometimes awkward for me when I speak.)

Furthermore, Participant 4 shared her experience of struggling with English fluency, which causes her to feel pressured and hesitant when conversing in the language. This lack of confidence has become a significant factor that intimidates her and hampers her language learning progress. The pressure to speak fluently and the fear of making mistakes contribute to her reluctance to engage in English conversations. She stated that:

“So, the specific challenges I have encountered in my language learning journey are first is, ang fluency sa English since, diba sir kanang sa kada klase namo is, diba as English majors, we are expected gyud nga mag practice, nga mag speak og English, so, sakong, I’m not that fluent gyud kung mag estorya kog English that’s why ako na syang ginaconsider nga challenge sa pag learn sa language.” (IDI-04)

(The specific challenges I have encountered in my language learning journey are, first, achieving fluency in English. In every class we have as English majors, we are expected to practice speaking English fluently. For me, I am not yet fluent when speaking English, which is why I consider it a challenge in learning the language.)

Moreover, Participant 1 emphasized the challenge of having pronunciation issues, which negatively impacts his learning experience. He expressed that these difficulties lead to hesitation in speaking, as he fears mispronouncing words could result in misunderstandings or even ridicule. This apprehension about making

mistakes causes him to hold back from participating fully in conversations. He stated:

“The difficulties that I’ve encountered as challenges is my pronunciation with regards to those words that I’ve encountered and also the pronunciation sad kay some of the words kay dili mao ang pag-pronounce kay kanang murag stranger pajud sya nga words sakong nya wala ko kabalo kung unsaon sya pag-pronuncemao lang, bali as learning as English major pud ah one of the difficulties that I had is the kuan lang jud pronunciation.” (IDI-01)

(The difficulties I have encountered include challenges with the pronunciation of certain words and pronunciation in general. Some words are not pronounced as expected and sound quite strange to me, making it hard to pronounce them correctly. As an English major, one of the difficulties I have faced is pronunciation.)

Lastly, stuttering while speaking impacts language learning negatively. This challenge leads to reduced engagement in speaking activities, as the participant feels self-conscious and uncomfortable. The frustration and embarrassment associated with stuttering contribute to a reluctance to use or speak in English. This issue creates a negative feeling towards language practice, hindering the development of fluency and confidence in English. Participant 7 stated that:

“kanang introvert ko nga person sa una like dijud ko ganahan og public kanang public communication then natingala ko nganong

nisulod ko aning teacher nga kanang introvert ta—dili ta ganahan og public communication. Ang kuan lang is kanang ma stutter ko kung muestorya ko.” (IDI-07)

(Initially, I was an introverted person who did not enjoy public communication. I was surprised to find myself in the teaching profession, as introverts typically do not favor public speaking. Additionally, I tend to stutter when I speak.)

External and Internal Factors in Language Learning. Participants in the interviews and focus groups identified factors influencing language learning, including external elements like resource availability, supportive environments, and exposure to native speakers. They stressed the importance of these factors in providing opportunities for practice and cultural immersion, essential for acquisition. Additionally, internal factors such as motivation, self-efficacy, and learning styles were discussed, with motivation being a central theme. Participants highlighted intrinsic and extrinsic motivators driving their engagement in language learning.

Restrained Language Learning Method. This one emerges as the fourth code identified within the first probed issue, as highlighted by participants in both individual in-depth interviews (IDI) and focus group discussions (FGD). Through their shared experiences, participants conveyed encountering challenges associated with this particular approach to language learning.

In that sense, one of the challenges encountered by the participants is the scarcity of English learning materials, which significantly impacts their language acquisition. The limited access to these resources has become a notable problem, as it restricts their opportunities to practice and improve their skills, creating obstacles in their educational journey. Similarly, Participant 3 said that:

“I would specify sa daghag challenges nga mga naano nako naencounter sa language learning is sa elementary, mainly naa—I studied in a school na multigrade so the arrangement is grade 1 and grade 2 is kanang together in one classroom, so, there there are many issues nu nga naencounter namo ato nga time. Una, scarcity sa learning materials.” (IDI-03)

(I would specify the numerous challenges I encountered in language learning during elementary school. Mainly, I studied in a multigrade school where grades 1 and 2 were together in one classroom. There were many issues we faced during that time. Firstly, there was a scarcity of learning materials.)

Furthermore, lacking exposure to authentic language use was also considered by the participants as a challenge of acquiring the language. They highlighted that the rarity of the direct exposure to the language use lessens the level of language learning. Language in the context is rarely observed, making students to only use English in academic context, indicating that practically speaking the language is less observed, leading to ineffective language learning. Similarly, Participant 4 stated that:

“Maglisod sad kog relate kay in the first place dili man ta native speaker sa English.” (IDI-04)

(It is also difficult for me to relate because, in the first place, we're not native English speakers.)

In similar code, Participants agreeably identified that lack of exposure to authentic language use poses a significant challenge in acquiring the language. The rarity of observing and practicing the language in natural contexts restricts their ability to develop practical language skills and fluency. This emphasizes the need for more immersive and varied language experiences to enhance learning. FGD 4 added that:

“Ang pag learn nako sa language is gina practice ra nako sa school which is deleted pud sa akong challenge sir ba kanang language usage skills. Of course, kay pag abot sa balay ug kauban sa akong friends kay dili man nako magamit ang kanang akong na learn jud ba nga specific gud, so, syempre kay murag na focus nagud sya, napractice lang sya sa school.” (FGD-04)

(My language learning primarily takes place in school, which poses a challenge for me regarding my language usage skills. When I get home and spend time with my friends, I am unable to apply what I have learned in a specific way. It seems that the practice is very focused and restricted to the school environment.)

Lack of Teaching Competence. This one emerges as the fifth code identified in the first exploration of language learning challenges by participants. The challenge of inadequate teaching competence is a pressing concern affecting the quality of learning experiences. One notable issue is the scarcity of teachers who are able to effectively impart knowledge and skills to their students. This shortage often results in a lack of educators who possess the necessary expertise to teach English comprehensively, including literature, grammar rules, and other essential components of the language.

Similarly, the availability of teachers who can effectively deliver instruction is a critical issue in education. Without skilled and competent educators, students may struggle to grasp key concepts, develop critical thinking skills, and reach their full potential. When teachers are not readily available or lack the necessary skills to engage and inspire students, the quality of education suffers, impacting academic achievement and long-term success. This problem arose and directly experienced specifically by the Participant 3, and stated that:

“There are many issues nu nga naencounter namo ato nga time. Una, scarcity sa learning materials. Ikaduha, availability of teachers nga effectively maka-teach sa language. Ikatulo is, kanang aside sa materials is that walay proper nga murag assessment gud if the learners are really learning the language effectively.” (IDI-03)

(There were many issues that we encountered during that time. First, there was a scarcity of learning materials. Second, there was a lack of teachers available who could effectively teach the language. Thirdly, aside from materials, there was no proper assessment to determine if the learners were really effectively learning the language.)

Moreover, the absence of English teachers who are deeply engaged in teaching the language comprehensively, encompassing literature, grammar rules, and other essential aspects, is a significant concern leading to a shallow English learning experience for students. English teachers who lack hands-on involvement in these aspects of teaching has led students to struggle in developing a deep appreciation for language and literature, as well as proficiency in grammar and communication skills. This challenge has personally experienced by Participant 3, and stated that:

“Among language teacher, dili sya ingana ka hands-on nga magteach, like abi lang man namo gud ato nga sa among language nga subject is pag language more in literature—reading, in-ana ana lang, then, karon supposed to be diay sa kato nga level namo sa secondary is supposed to be kabalo nami sa mga kanang rules, grammar, so, what happened is, we are more on reading but we are not more on the learning of the specifications of the rules.” (IDI-03)

(Our language teacher was not very hands-on in teaching. We mainly focused on literature and reading comprehension rather than exploring the technicalities of grammar and language rules. Now, at our current level in secondary school, we should have a deeper understanding of grammar rules and language intricacies. However, our focus has primarily been on reading, and we have not delved into the specifics of language rules and technicalities as much as we should have.)

School System Restructuring. This is the sixth code in the first probed issue, and is seen as a challenge for the students in their learning. The incorporation of blended learning, combining face-to-face instruction with online components, has presented challenges, particularly in the context of language learning. The shift to blended learning offers flexibility and access to resources, however, it has also introduced complexities that lessens the meaningfulness of language learning session especially when Participant 3 stated that:

“Murag nag shift ta into blended nga ano nga learning—supposed to be every week we are able to grasp learnings or lessons and then what happened is online, and then dili all teachers are able to conduct online classes because of the internet. Siguro if we were given that enough time nga mag study jud siguro mas meaningful, mas masabtan ug mas ma embrace nato ang lessons.” (IDI-03)

(It appears that we have shifted to blended learning. Ideally, we should be able to grasp lessons every week. However, due to the transition to online classes, not all teachers are able to conduct them effectively because of internet limitations. Perhaps, if we were given sufficient time to study the language, we would find the lessons more meaningful, understandable, and easier to embrace.)

Psychological Issues. This code emerged as the seventh in the first probed issue. This challenges students in English language learning that include feeling pressured to speak fluently by teachers' expectations, anxiety about making grammatical mistakes, and fear of judgment from classmates, particularly those majoring in English. These factors contribute to reluctance in engaging with spoken English activities and hinder language development.

Similarly, becoming pressured on the teacher's expectation in speaking English fluently pressures the participants that can create a sense of performance anxiety, leading to self-doubt and fear of making mistakes. As to, students have become reluctant to engage in spoken English activities, hindering their language development. This has personally experienced by Participant 3 who stated that:

“Mag ask og question amoang instructor, we speak in English jud ba like fluent gud. Ang expectations sa instructor ba kay dapat ma-meet gud. Like ma pressure man gud mi mga students like ana gud.” (IDI-06)

(When it comes that our instructor asks us and they expect us to speak English fluently and meet their expectations. It can be quite pressuring for us as students.)

Lastly, being anxious in speaking in fear of committing mistakes in grammar and afraid of being judged by English major classmates. The participants have experienced this problem and see it a great challenge for them in learning and at the same time using the language. This fear hampers their willingness to engage in spoken English activities, hindering language development. As what FGD 7 shared:

“Mahadlok pud ko nga ma judge sa akong mga classmates especially that they are English majors, so, isa pud na sya ka reason.” (FGD-07)

(I am also afraid of being judged by my classmates, especially since they are English majors. That is also one of the reasons.)

Personality Traits. Emerged as the eighth code under the first probed issue. This presents significant challenges in the context of language learning. This factor affects the language learning process of the learners as they tend to become less motivated intrinsically in learning the language, making them become less engaged or get involved in language-related activities.

Similarly, introverted individuals may feel more comfortable in solitary activities and may struggle with initiating or sustaining conversations in group settings. And, having no passion for public communication, participant finds it difficult to engage in public speaking or networking events, further exacerbating feelings of discomfort and self-doubt. Additionally, low self-esteem can undermine their confidence in social interactions, leading to a reluctance to express opinions or assert themselves. This problem negatively hindered the absorption of language learning, making the student so challenged in his language learning journey. He stated that:

“Kanang introvert ko nga person sa una like dijud ko ganahan og public kanang public communication then natingala ko nganong nisulod ko aning teacher nga kanang introvert ta—dili ta ganahan og public communication.” (IDI-07)

(I used to be an introverted person who really disliked public communication. I am surprised why I entered this profession as a teacher, considering that introverts like us typically dislike public communication.)

Mastery in Instructional and Content Delivery. Participants from in-depth interviews and focus group discussion highlighted the importance of mastery of the instructional and contents to be delivered to the learners. When teachers adhere to this characteristic, students can clearly and precisely understand what is taught to them. In here, the participants had shared that clear language instruction could greatly impact to their learning of the language.

Clear Language Instruction. This is the first code in the second probed issue. From the gathered responses both from FGD and IDI, the participants shared that teachers who have clear instructions in delivering the lesson positively give them a sense of effective understanding towards the topic. Providing clear explanations by articulating concepts in a straightforward manner, using accessible language and examples that resonate with learners' experiences. Clear explanations help students grasp the underlying principles of language use and reinforce their understanding.

Similarly, providing thorough information on sentence construction techniques can greatly enhance learners' understanding of language. By employing accessible language and using relatable examples drawn from students' everyday experiences, educators can bridge the gap between unfamiliar academic concepts and students' existing knowledge. This approach makes abstract concepts more concrete and comprehensible, allowing students to grasp and apply sentence structures more effectively. Such tailored instruction helps students connect theoretical knowledge with practical application, thereby improving their overall language proficiency and confidence. As stated by Participant 1:

“The teachers play a vital role kay especially nu sila man ang nakahibalo, ang expert so when the teachers give clear explanations thorough or mga information nga what are the techniques nga unsaon namo pag construct and is aka sentence.” (IDI-01)

(The teachers play a vital role because they are the experts. When teachers provide clear and thorough explanations or information, and demonstrate the techniques we should use to construct sentences, it greatly enhances our understanding and ability to apply what we have learned.)

Correspondingly, providing clear explanations empowers students to understand and engage with academic material more comprehensively of which participants emphasized the pivotal role of clear instructions in fostering a conducive learning environment. Teachers who adeptly deliver lessons with clarity provide students with a roadmap for understanding complex topics positively impacts their learning experiences. This is evident to FGD 1 as she stated that:

“I believe that teachers contribute to addressing these challenges by uhhh providing clear explanations and also they offer values or diverse learning materials which can create opportunities for us to practice and interact with our peers and also our co-students in using the lang—english language.” (FGD-01)

(I believe that teachers contribute to addressing these challenges by providing clear explanations. They also offer a variety of learning materials which create opportunities for us to practice and interact with our peers and classmates in using the English language.)

Lastly, explaining the concept or highfalutin word using accessible language and relatable examples drawn from students' everyday experiences, educators bridge the gap between unfamiliar academic concepts and students' existing knowledge base. This approach not only facilitates understanding but also enhances retention and application of learned material. Consequently, FGD-02 stated that:

“Sa mga naexperience nako, highfalutin words, kailangan gyud sya iexplain ni teacher for the students na makasabot sila sa concept or sa word kung unsa na sya para makasabot sya ug ma use tu nimo na words in using the language po.” (FGD-02)

(In my experience, when encountering complex or sophisticated words, it is crucial for the teacher to explain them thoroughly so that students can understand the concept or the word itself. This approach enables students to comprehend and effectively use these words in their language usage.)

Transfer of Knowledge and Learning. This is the second code in the second probed issue. This serves as the backbone of language acquisition, equipping learners with the necessary knowledge and skills to effectively communicate and comprehend. Through this process, educators play a crucial role in guiding and transmitting knowledge, enabling students to understand and internalize lessons.

Similarly, the participants see teachers as individuals who do not just impart knowledge to them but as well facilitate their learnings. They see educators as the backbone in language education, providing the essential foundation for equipping them with the knowledge and skills necessary for effective communication. This is evident to Participant 2, and stated that:

“Okay, so, teachers are fundamentally the advisers or sila gyud atong backbone in terms of learning especially in school, they really are the ones who will equip us more in the special—especially sa mga butang nga maglisod pata. So, teachers are that important to learn really the language.” (IDI-02)

(Yes, teachers are fundamentally advisers and serve as the backbone of our learning, especially in school. They are the ones who equip us, particularly in areas where we struggle. Therefore, teachers are crucial for truly learning and mastering the language.)

Correspondingly, guiding and transmitting knowledge are pivotal roles in education, crucial for helping students understand lessons effectively. Educators act as facilitators, leading students through the learning process with clear direction, support, and relevant resources. They provide the necessary tools and strategies to aid comprehension, ensuring that students can grasp and apply new concepts. Also, students prior understanding will be strengthened because of the ideas transmitted by the teachers to the learners. This encounter was personally experienced by Participant 4, she shared that:

“That teachers contribute to addressing the challenges and hurdles I have faced in language learning, sir, since sila mna gud tung tao nga mag embark satoag knowledge. For example, dili ta kasabot sa mga lessons, so, sila gyud tung expected nga tao nga mag guide satoa para masabtan nato ang mga lessons.” (IDI-04)

(Teachers contribute significantly to addressing the challenges and hurdles I have faced in language learning because they impart knowledge, guide us, and help us understand the lessons. For example, when we do not understand certain lessons, they are the individuals who guide us to comprehend them.)

Lastly, becoming knowledgeable and adept in a language is a foundational prerequisite for effective language instruction that teacher should possess to effectively teach concepts. By demonstrating fluency and proficiency, educators instill a sense of authenticity and credibility in their teaching, which fosters trust and respect among students. Participant 7 emphasized that:

“I believe that they can help me addressing my challenges in learning the language because as a teacher, dapat knowledgeable ka about sa that particular language kay you can’t teach children you didn’t know---ahhh dili ka mutudlo og mga bata na dika kabalo unsay itudlo.” (IDI-07)

(I believe that teachers can help me address my challenges in learning the language because, as educators, they should be knowledgeable about the language they are teaching. You cannot effectively teach children something you do not know.)

Teaching Strategies. This is the third code in the second probed issue. Implementing diverse teaching strategies plays a crucial role in fostering a dynamic and engaging learning environment. Strategies such as employing "last man standing" during oral recitation inject an element of excitement and competition into language lessons, motivating students to actively participate and demonstrate their language skills.

Similarly, employing strategies like “last man standing” during oral recitation is an effective technique to engage students and promote active participation in language learning. In this strategy, students take turns answering questions or reciting information. This approach introduces an element of competition and excitement, motivating students to prepare and engage with the material actively. This scenario was experienced and encountered personally by Participant 6 who firmly stated that:

“Kana ilahang mga strashsegy—strategies gud sir kung unsaon nila pag mag oral recitation, maggamit sila strategy like last man standing chuchuchuchu mga ing’ana gud. Dili sya effective way but isa sya sa mga strategy para kami mga students is naa mi maanswer o naa pud mi makat-onan ba.” (IDI-06)

(Their strategies for conducting lessons, such as using techniques like "last man standing" during oral recitations, are examples of how they engage students. While these strategies may not always be the most effective, they provide opportunities for us students to answer questions and learn something new.)

Moreover, serving as a guide by offering scaffolding is a fundamental aspect of facilitating an effective language learning journey for students that teacher should consider. Scaffolding involves providing structured support and guidance to learners as they engage with new language concepts and skills. By serving as guides and facilitators of learning through scaffolding, teachers can help students develop the necessary competencies in their language learning journey and beyond. FGD 5 stated:

“I also believe that teachers help in addressing the challenge I face because they serve as a guide who offers scaffolding especially for me, to have an effective language learning journey.” (IDI-05)

(I also believe that teachers help in addressing the challenges I face because they serve as guides who offer scaffolding, especially for me, to have an effective language learning journey.)

In line with same code, as scaffolding involves providing structured support and guidance to students, it engages them with new language concepts and skills. This approach helps learners gradually build their understanding and capabilities, allowing them to tackle increasingly complex tasks with confidence. This method ensures that students are not only acquiring knowledge but also gaining the skills to apply and adapt it independently. FGD-06 stated that:

“Teachers should use scaffolding nu as one of their means of instruction since need ni sa student as kaning guidance jud when it comes to learning language. We are not ignorant of the fact na English is not our first language and learning the language itself is really difficult samot na nga dili sya atuang native language.” (FGD-06)

(Teachers should use scaffolding as a key method of instruction, especially when it comes to learning a language that is not our first language. Learning a new language is inherently challenging, so it is crucial for teachers to provide scaffolding to effectively learn the language.)

Lastly, devising a rule that mandates the utilization of English in the classroom is a proactive strategy for creating an immersive language learning environment. By establishing clear expectations for language use, teachers set the tone for communication and interaction within the classroom. This rule encourages students to consistently practice using English in various contexts, whether it's during class discussions, group activities, or even informal conversations. In line with this, FGD-07 emphasized that:

“Isa pud sa akong naexperience personally na teacher is the main reason nganong mag use ko’g English language kay ginapugos or like gihimo syang rule sa ano...sa classroom setting namo para maggamit or makatuon mi og gamit og English language.” (FGD-07)

(Another personal experience I have had with a teacher is the main reason why I use the English language. It was because she enforced it as a rule in our classroom setting for us to use and learn to use the English language.)

Engaging and Vibrant Learning Environment. In response to the gathered data from both IDI and FGD, the participants responded that an engaging and vibrant learning environment is essential for fostering effective language learning and sustaining students' interest in language acquisition. This involves employing a variety of strategies to capture students' attention, promote active participation, and cultivate a positive learning atmosphere.

Interactive Group-based Activity. This is the first code under the third probed issue. In accordance to the responses compiled from the in-depth interviews and focus group discussion, the participants have shared their ideas pinpointing the impact of this category in the learning process. Interactive group-based activities not only make learning more enjoyable and engaging but also provide valuable opportunities for social interaction, peer support, and collaborative problem-solving, and enhancing the overall language learning experience.

Correspondingly, having activities like conversation or dialogue in English is one of the activities considered by the participant in engaging into language learning process. Incorporating activities as such is paramount for fostering active engagement and promoting language acquisition. By facilitating conversations or dialogues, teachers create a dynamic and interactive learning environment where students can actively participate and practice their speaking and listening skills. This is agreeable to Participant 1 as he stated that:

“Personally sa specific intances that I have encountered, one of the app—siguro one of the approach nga akong giganahan or makahatag sakog interest is kanang naay mga mga naa mi activities ba—naay activities sa language and kanang naa man guy mga conversation or dialogue nga in English so ma challenge pud ko.” (IDI-01)

(Personally, in specific instances I have encountered, I have found that engaging in activities that involve conversations or dialogues in English has sparked my interest. These activities challenge me and enhance my language learning experience.)

In addition, providing authentic activities such as role-play with constructive feedback is a powerful strategy for promoting language learning and engagement. This hands-on approach not only enhances students' language skills but also fosters creativity and critical thinking. Incorporating constructive feedback into role-play activities is essential for promoting continuous improvement and language development, effective in instilling lasting and meaningful learnings among the learners. With this, Participant 4 stated that:

“Sa ilahang approach nga kanang feel nako is nag impact sakoa, especially sakong interest and engagement sa language studies is mga activities, like authentic and group activities such as role play, kana gud sir. Through ana nga approach nila is magka interest ko to learn the language specifically English, and of course, naa pud silay constructive feedback nga makahatag sako kanang ‘guide to do that’ para maimprove akoang pag learn sa language.” (IDI-04)

(In their approach, I feel that it has positively impacted my interest and engagement in language studies. For instance, activities like authentic group activities and role plays have sparked my interest in learning English. Additionally, the constructive feedback they provide guides me on areas where I need to improve in my language learning.)

Furthermore, employing a group-based strategy with each member delegated with tasks leading to cooperation and lesson is a highly effective approach for promoting collaborative learning and enhancing language acquisition. This strategy involves dividing students into small groups and assigning each member specific tasks or roles related to the lesson objective. By working together towards a common goal, students engage in cooperative learning experiences that facilitate active participation, critical thinking, and communication skills development. Participant 6 stated that:

“Katong gigamit niya nga strategy sir ba in which nga gi grupo-grupo mi niya—tapos each group is gitagaan mi niyag task nga himoon in a specific time, so kato sir makita gyud nako nga tanan member sa group is nag—cooperate, and ddtu, nahimo namo amoang task—and naanswer namo ang mga task and mao tu—nakahatag sya samoag lesson pud.” (IDI-06)

(The strategy she used, where she grouped us and assigned specific tasks to each group within a certain timeframe, was very effective. I observed that all group members actively cooperated, allowing us to complete our tasks efficiently and answer the assigned questions. Additionally, it provided us with a valuable lesson.)

Lastly, incorporating interactive activities that would allow everyone to feel included in the discussion is a powerful strategy for promoting engagement, participation, and language acquisition. These activities create a supportive and inclusive learning environment where all students have the opportunity to contribute and learn from one another. As what stated by FGD-06, she shared that:

“Teacher’s approach significantly impacted my interest and engagement in language learning through nag incorporate gani silag mga interactive activities, also, kana gani pong ginapafeel nila nga everyone is included in the discussion. Through that, ma boost akoang confidence to speak, of course in English language because we are trained inside the classroom to speak the language itself.” (FGD-06)

(One specific instance where a teacher's approach significantly impacted my interest and engagement in language learning was when they incorporated interactive activities. They ensured that everyone felt included in the discussion. This approach boosted my confidence in speaking, especially in English, because we were encouraged to actively participate. The classroom training to speak the language further enhanced our skills.)

Positive Learning Climate. This is the second code in the third probed issue. It pertains to the overall atmosphere and environment within a classroom or educational setting that fosters student engagement, motivation, and well-being. This aspect crucially played a role in the teaching-learning process. In such atmosphere, students feel safe, supported, and valued, which enhances their willingness to participate and explore new ideas.

Similarly, manifesting a positive environment for learning, such as being open to questions and clarification, is a fundamental aspect of fostering a supportive and inclusive classroom atmosphere. This is considered to be vital in the context of language learning, allowing students to express their thoughts without hesitating because of negatives criticisms from the surroundings. This is agreed by Participant 3 as he stated that:

“Kanang ang teacher mismo kay muhatag sya og positive environment for learning. Naa man gud tay teacher, nga ma-intimidate ta instead nga maka open for questions supposed to be or given the chance nga makapangutana, there are teachers man gud nga dili sila ing-ana ka conducive ang vibe to ask questions. So, as learner, dapat mahatag na satoa nga opportunity to ask questions or clarifications with ideas nga naa sa atoaang mind kay we are always curious man.” (IDI-03)

(It is important for teachers to create a positive learning environment where students feel comfortable asking questions. Sometimes, we encounter teachers who are intimidating, which makes it difficult for us to feel open about seeking clarification. As learners, we should have the opportunity to ask questions and clarify ideas because we are naturally curious and constantly learning. Therefore, it is crucial for teachers to foster an environment where students feel encouraged to engage and seek guidance.)

Additionally, recognizing students' answers is a crucial in fostering a positive learning environment and promoting student engagement and confidence. Recognizing students' answers is a simple yet powerful practice that contributes to a positive learning environment and promotes student engagement, confidence, and academic growth. By acknowledging students' answer and providing positive reinforcement, they tend to become more participative and not hesitant in expressing their ideas. Participant 5 stated that:

“What makes me interested in learning the language would be when teacher integrated activities or teacher recognizes answers. I would say I am very much open pud sa criticism or feedback na ihatag sa teachers po. And more likely I would say na there’s a lot of things or room for improvement for everything—on learning that language po, sir.” (IDI-05)

(I believe what makes me interested in learning the language is when the teacher integrates activities and recognizes my answers. I am very much open to criticism or feedback from teachers. I would say that there is always room for improvement in learning the language, and I am willing to work on that.)

Correspondingly, creating a comfortable environment for students to speak and utilize English without fear of being judged on grammar mistakes is essential for fostering language fluency, confidence, and communication skills. This allows the participants to express their thoughts without hesitation that negative judgment from the environment may arise. With this, an emphasis toward a conducive, friendly and constructive learning environment must be highly manifested to ensure effective language learning process. FGD-03 stated that:

“One specific instance nu sa teacher’s approach kay—naka impact jud sa akoang motivation in learning the language or language studies kay when they create an environment where I can feel comfortable in speaking or utilizing the language itself. With that, by creating that positive environment in learning, I can uhhh...maka express gani ko sakong self without feeling uncomfortable nga they will judge me when my grammar and...sa kanang other things nga kanang akoang pronunciation, ana gud. So, that’s it sa ing’ana.” (FGD-03)

(One specific instance of a teacher's approach that significantly impacted my motivation in learning the language was when they created an environment where I felt comfortable speaking and using the language. By fostering a positive learning atmosphere, I was able to express myself without feeling uncomfortable or fearing judgment regarding my grammar, pronunciation, and other aspects of language use.)

Lastly, creating a good and positive environment thru giving feedback in a friendly manner is essential for promoting student

confidence, motivation, and growth. Supporting and encouraging learners in such way fosters a sense of trust, respect, and rapport between teachers and students. Becoming soft and gentle in giving feedbacks would make the participants be expressive and not hesitant in speaking the language. In accordance with this, FGD-07 stated that:

“In my personal experience, I have experienced that most of the teachers create a good, positive environment *kanang* when it comes to giving feedback, *dili siya ingon nga kanang lain nga pagka feedback nga wrong—wrong grahams ka ing’ana gud like casual lang nga pagka hatag og feedback nga dili pud nga makapasakit sa akong damdamin.*” (FGD-07)

(In my personal experience, I have found that most teachers create a positive environment when giving feedback. They provide feedback in a way that does not feel harsh or hurtful but rather in a casual manner that does not affect my feelings negatively.)

Real-life Language Application. This is the third code under the third probed issue. This approach emphasizes the practical application of language learning in real-world contexts, such as social interactions and daily activities. By creating opportunities for students to use their language skills in everyday situations, educators empower them to become confident and proficient speakers. Engaging with the language outside of academic exercises allows students to practice and refine their skills in meaningful ways, leading to greater fluency and practical competence. This hands-on experience helps bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and real-world use, enhancing overall language proficiency.

Correspondingly, incorporating real-world examples and cultural insights into language learning is paramount for fostering a comprehensive understanding of the target language and the cultural context. By bringing authentic experiences and cultural nuances into the classroom, the students adhere to effective language learning. FGD-01 stated that:

“Certain instance where my teacher’s approach significantly impacted my interest is when my teacher or some teachers incorporate engaging teaching styles and also, they incorporate real-world examples and cultural insights that has significantly boosted my interest and engagement in language studies. So, as we all know that English is not only focusing on the language learning but also in the application or the language usage that can be used in real life communication.” (FGD-01)

(A specific instance where my teacher's approach significantly impacted my interest was when some teachers incorporated engaging teaching styles, real-world examples, and cultural insights. These strategies significantly boosted my interest and engagement in language studies. English is not just about language learning but also about its application in real-life communication, and these approaches highlighted that aspect effectively.)

Lastly, focusing on the application of language in real-life situations is effective in language instruction. By emphasizing practical usage over rote memorization, educators empower students to communicate confidently and effectively in various everyday contexts. Incorporating real-life scenarios like using the language in giving answers or during oral recitation enables students to apply their language skills authentically, reinforcing comprehension and fluency. Further, using English at home or in daily basis highly ensure retention of learning as it is frequently used and practiced by the learner. As FGD-02 stated that:

“*Katong approach ni teacher nu na we should as English major student, we should use English language. Kanang kung mag answer mi sa kanang mga task or activities sa classroom setting bitaw, kanang mag recite—mag recite mi so by that, kanang, murag ma improve gyud ang kanang language learning namo. Ma learn gyud namo sya kay ma-use man namo ang language, maexpose sa language na ano ginatudlo. Kanang kumbaga ginaapply na namo ang among natun’an ba, dili kay puro lang naa sa hunahuna.*” (FGD-02)

(The approach where we, as English majors, are encouraged to use English when answering or reciting in the classroom significantly enhances language learning. This practice increases our exposure and familiarity with the language being taught. Here, we really learn effectively as we are practically using the language already.)

Group Speaking Activities. In response to the gathered data from both IDI and FGD, the participants responded to the idea that group speaking activities plays a crucial role in enhancing teacher effectiveness and fostering language interest among students. These activities promote active participation, collaboration, and peer interaction, creating a supportive and engaging learning environment.

Group Discussion. This is the first code in the fourth probed issue. This aspect recognizes the pivotal role of group discussions in enhancing both teacher effectiveness and student interest in language learning. Group discussions promote effective teaching by encouraging interactive and collaborative learning, allowing students to engage with the material actively. These discussions can ignite students' passion for the language, making the learning process more dynamic and engaging. Fostering an environment where students feel comfortable sharing and exploring ideas, group discussions enhance their overall educational experience and motivation to learn.

Correspondingly, having group discussions like brainstorming with classmates is a strategy that participants are using in grasping concepts having deep underlying meanings. This way of understanding topics or lessons fosters collaboration among them, creating a rapport and togetherness in unveiling the ideas conveyed. Participant 4 stated that:

“For me, the particular teaching methods or activities that I find effective in fostering my interest in language is group discussions, like *kanang mag brainstorming mi together with my classmates, so, I think mao pud na ang teaching methods or activities nga kanang murag makita nako ba nga something effective gud when it comes to really learning the language effectively and meaningfully.*” (IDI-04)

(For me, the particular teaching methods or activities that I find effective in fostering my interest in language include group discussions and brainstorming sessions with my classmates. I believe these teaching methods or activities are effective because I have personally seen positive results in my language learning journey effective and meaningful.)

Speaking Tasks or Activities. This is the second code under the fourth probed issue. The responses provided by the participants have come up into the idea that learning the language through various speaking activities such as debate, impromptu, extempo, and the likes would effectively embark learning. These performances allow the students to practically and directly use the language, making them speak the language actually.

Additionally, incorporating debate, extemporaneous speaking is seen as a good way of practicing to speak the language. Given that the students are tasked to speak up, probably in English, student now have this direct use of the language to generate ideas and construct sentences in conveying their understanding. FGD 6 stated that:

“I think that there are a lot of teaching methods or activities that I find effective in fostering my interest in language such as teachers incorporating debate or extemporaneous speaking, of course, and also discussion within group members nu kay through that uhmh maka—ay maka use ko sa uhm English language and it interests me also to participate in class.” (FGD-06)

(I believe there are many teaching methods or activities that effectively foster my interest in language, such as teachers incorporating debates, extemporaneous speaking, and group discussions. Through these activities, I am able to use the English language and it also interests me to participate actively in class discussions.)

Moreover, engaging in impromptu speaking ignites participants' enthusiasm for using the language, as it requires them to speak spontaneously and think on their feet. This approach encourages students to actively use the language in real-time situations, enhancing their fluency and confidence. By participating in impromptu speaking activities, students become more directly involved in the learning process, making the language practice more dynamic and interactive. This hands-on engagement helps solidify their language skills and fosters a greater sense of ownership over their learning experience. As Participant 7 stated, he shared that:

“Effective jud sya labi nag activities like kanang impromptu speaking or kanang activity nga included ang participation sa students nga magestorya sa atubangan through gamit sa medium sa English.” (IDI-07)

(It is indeed effective, especially with activities like impromptu speaking or those that involve active participation, where students are encouraged to share stories or speak in front using English as the medium. These activities not only improve language skills but also boost confidence in using the language.)

Lastly, using reader's theatre as an assessment for vocabulary skills allows learners to apply their vocabulary in a practical context, enhancing their grasp of concepts and terminologies. By participating in reader's theatre, students use their vocabulary actively as they portray characters and engage with the text. This method not only helps them understand and use new words but also provides a platform for self-assessment. Participant 1 stated that:

“Siguro kaning mga readers theater—one of the activities, in English kay mao man pud nay not only assessing our vocabulary in English but also gina assess pud nato unsa atong confidence to portray our portray our character.” (IDI-01)

(Certainly, activities like reader's theater are effective because they not only assess our vocabulary in English but also evaluate our confidence in portraying characters. It is a holistic approach to language learning that incorporates both linguistic skills and communication abilities.)

Teacher's Teaching Competence. In accordance to the gathered responses both from IDI and FGD, this theme is fundamental to both teacher effectiveness and student language interest. Competent educators not only deliver high-quality instruction but also inspire and empower students to become confident, proficient, and lifelong learners of language. Their expertise, dedication, and passion create a dynamic and enriching learning experience that positively impacts student willingness, achievement, engagement, and overall language proficiency.

Pedagogical Knowledge. This is the first code under the fifth probed issue. From the responses posited by both in-depth interviews and focus group discussion, it had come up to the ideas concerning the importance of pedagogical knowledge that represents the teacher's comprehensive understanding of effective teaching methodologies and strategies specifically tailored to language learning. With a solid grasp of pedagogical principles, educators can adeptly design and implement instructional plans that captivate students' interest and facilitate language acquisition.

Correspondingly, ensuring one's expertise in language teaching allows learners to substantially learn concepts and ideas contributory to their learning development. Teachers' ability and expertise with what they are teaching upholds concrete understanding for the students' end. They embark meaningful learnings to the learners, signifying their vital role in the teaching-learning process. As to, Participant 1 shared that:

“I believe the teachers could further enhance the effectiveness of their language instruction ahhmm most among kuan is makita gyud namo ang usa ka teacher naa sya expertise in terms of in terms of her or his teaching upon us so—also kanang makita namo ang

kanang ay especially akoa personally kay ka Maam L, I really admire maam nga the way sya mu-construct og message nga han'ay mu-construct og ideas.” (IDI-01)

(I believe teachers could further enhance the effectiveness of their language instruction, especially when they demonstrate expertise in constructing messages and ideas clearly. Personally, I admire Ma'am L for her skill in this area.)

In addition, serving as an inspiration to enhance language skills through demonstrated competence significantly contributes to igniting participants' interest and eagerness to learn. When educators and peers showcase their own proficiency and passion for the language, it can motivate students to strive for similar levels of skill. This demonstration of competence not only highlights the possibilities of language mastery but also encourages students to engage more deeply with their learning process. In line with this, FGD-07 stated that:

“For me is mga teachers kay sila ang mahimong inspiration nako k aysila man ang mas hasa ana na language so sila akong inspiration na para mas ma boost akong interest sa language.” (FGD-07)

(For me, my teachers serve as my inspiration because they are more proficient in the language. They inspire me to further develop my interest and boost my enthusiasm for language learning.)

Lastly, being equipped and having mastery in teaching is crucial for gaining the trust and confidence of participants while they learn the language. This competence reassures learners that they are receiving accurate and valuable instruction, fostering a sense of security and motivation in their educational journey. Educators' expertise towards the subject matter creates a reliable learning environment where students feel confident that they are acquiring the necessary skills and knowledge. With this, Participant stated that:

“Well, for me, sir, ah I agree nga teachers as they are equip gyud sya og kanang naa gyuy mastery sa ilang ah ilang teaching para matudlo sa ilang estudyante ang unsay dapat makat-onan nila.” (IDI-07)

(Well, for me, sir, I agree that teachers are equipped with mastery in their teaching methods to instruct their students on what they need to learn.)

Technology Integration. This is the second code under the fifth probed issue. The responses provided by the participants of both IDI and FGD have asserted that integrating technology offers innovative ways to engage students and enhance learning outcomes. Embracing technology integration, educators can create dynamic and immersive learning environments that prepare students for success in the digital age while fostering their language proficiency and overall academic growth.

Similarly, engaging students to simulation thru technology like online interview for assessment of English skills is seen by the participants to be a good way of preparing themselves in facing the digital age. This aspect engages students in using and integrating the modern invention into their studies not just in complying with the academic tasks but as well as honing their language speaking skills, allowing themselves to be more engaged and exposed to the modern inventions in honing and enhancing their language skills. As to, FGD-01 stated that:

“Teachers could enhance their effectiveness by incorporating more interactive, hands-on activities that provide constructive feedback that can also cater the individual learning styles and interest of students when engaging online interviews or online conversations in assessing my language skill.” (FGD-01)

(I think teachers could enhance their effectiveness by incorporating more interactive and hands-on activities that provide constructive feedback. They can also cater to the individual learning styles and interests of students by using engaging online interviews or conversations to assess language skills.)

Lastly, integrating technology in instruction for 21st century learners is vital to be employed in the academic context as learners of today's age are inclined with the modern inventions, making them find themselves effectively learn the language when there is this technology integration in the process. Students view the vital role technology is playing in their learning. As to, FGD-03 stated that:

“I believe na teachers could further enhance the effectiveness of their language instruction nu in boosting the interest and enthusiasm of the students in learning the language when they incorporate nu or integrate technologies nu as we all know na we are now in the 21st century nu, we are 21st century learners so, we are much more ah we—we'll be more motivated nu and inspired when we see or we can relate to the instructions that they will be integrating po.” (FGD-03)

(I believe that teachers could further enhance the effectiveness of their language instruction by boosting students' interest and enthusiasm through the integration of technology. As 21st-century learners, we are much more motivated and inspired when we can relate to instructions that incorporate modern technological tools and methods.)

Assessment and Evaluation. This is the third code under the fifth probed issue. Participants have mentioned that assessing and evaluating the learnings of the students are vital to their development in language learning. This aspect signifies the role of the teacher as the individuals who are in-charge in checking the progress of the learnings of their learners.

Similarly, conducting assessments and evaluations to understand what to change and enhance implies the idea that monitoring learners' progress helps guide teachers in selecting appropriate learning materials and lessons. Regular assessment allows educators to identify

areas where students excel and where they may struggle, providing valuable insights into their learning needs. By understanding these progress markers, teachers can tailor their instruction to better address gaps in knowledge and reinforce strengths. With this, FGD-05 stated that:

“So, I believe that my teachers could further enhance the effectiveness of their language instruction to better boost my interest and enthusiasm in learning the language through their evaluation because through their evaluation, they are aware of what to change and what to enhance, and because of that mas ma improve nila ang ilahang ahh instruction, ma reconstruct nila in a way that ma fit siya sa learning needs.” (FGD-05)

(I believe that my teachers could further enhance the effectiveness of their language instruction to better boost my interest and enthusiasm in learning the language through their evaluations. Through evaluations, they become aware of what needs to be changed and what needs to be enhanced. Because of that, they can improve their instruction, reconstructing it in a way that fits our learning needs.)

Lastly, knowing the students’ strengths and weaknesses to provide feedback for growth and development in language is essential in addressing their specific learning needs. By identifying these areas, educators can tailor their instruction to focus on the aspects that require improvement, ensuring a more efficient and effective learning process. This targeted feedback helps learners understand what they need to enhance and improve. With this, FGD-06 stated that:

“So, I believe nu that teachers could further enhance the effectiveness of their language instruction through knowing their students better because through that they will be able to know what are the strengths and weaknesses. Teachers provide feedback about the improvement of their language learning.” (FGD-06)

(I believe that teachers could further enhance the effectiveness of their language instruction by getting to know their students better. Through this understanding, they can identify strengths and weaknesses and provide feedback to facilitate growth and improvement in language learning.)

Coping Mechanism Shared of English Education Students with Regard to Handling Challenges and Maintaining Interest in Language Learning on the Varying Levels of Teachers’ Effectiveness

Six essential themes were derived from in-depth interviews and focus group discussions conducted with participants in response to the first research question. Before presenting the findings, profiles of participants for the qualitative data collection were provided in Table 3.1. This table presented the profiles of participants selected purposively, meeting inclusion criteria of being a 1st year, 2nd year, 3rd year, and 4th year English major education students in KCAST. The profiles were categorized based on participants' year level.

Additionally, Table 4.1 explored the coping mechanisms of English teacher education students with their experiences encountered concerning teacher effectiveness and language interest. The table presented essential themes derived from transcriptions of participants' responses to research question number one. These themes encompass overarching concepts summarized within the table.

Table 4.1. *Ways of Handling Challenges and Maintaining Interest in Language Learning on the Varying Levels of Teachers’ Effectiveness*

<i>Probed Issues</i>	<i>Core Ideas</i>	<i>Code/ Category</i>	<i>Essential Themes</i>	<i>Theoretical Perspectives</i>
Way of keeping strong interest in language education with teachers’ method mismatching learning style	Employing self-directed learning through initiating online searching.	Searching through Online and Library	Utilizing Research Skills with Technological Intervention	Technology-Enhanced Language Learning Theory
	Searching online			
	Going to library in learning the language	Utilizing Apps and Website		
	Seeking websites and online platforms that can enhance language skills			
	Seeking out additional resources like language app and searching online			
	Using phone applications that teach language	Supportive Friends	Establishing Social Support Network	
	Seeking assistance from friends by helping me understand the concept.			
Seeking assistance and sharing ideas with friends				
Asking friends with their understanding about a certain topic to stay interested in learning the language	Teacher’s Assistance			
Seeking assistance from teachers by asking their ideas or perspectives towards something.				
Moments of using coping	Encountering words that are difficult to	Encountering	Challenging	Cognitive Load Theory

strategies to handle challenges on language instruction effectiveness	understand Feeling “left behind” because of having difficulty in understanding highfalutin words	Unfamiliar Vocabulary	Linguistic Material	
	Having lessons that are very difficult already to grasp and understand Having topic is beyond to the capacity to understand	Confronting Difficult Material		
Managing stress or frustration with teacher’s approach that do not foster language interest	Diverting attention by optimistically perceiving things, learning, and enjoying life without losing hope Having optimistic characteristic and maintaining positive outlook in life	Optimism	Stress Management Techniques	Transactional Model of Stress and Coping
	Having a rest by stopping from doing anything and continue when everything seems fine again Taking a rest and bond with friends and family to relax	Rest and Relaxation		
Support System to Cope with challenges related to Teacher Effectiveness to Language Education	Being reminded about language learning goals and achievement of academic goals and objectives	Intrinsic Motivation	Language Learning Motivation	Self-Determination Theory
	Being reminded with the goals, that there’s so much to learn without total reliance to teachers Intrinsically motivating and reminding oneself with the benefits and advantages of language learning			
	Be motivated by the goals and by the family as an inspiration Having helped and influenced by friends to become motivated in learning	Extrinsic Motivation		
	Having families and friends as support systems Seeking support from family and friends Asking assistance, support and guidance from friends in learning the language Having friends and family to keep motivated to learn the language Seeking advice from the instructors who have vast knowledge in improving language learning	Social Support		
	Having technology, internet, and online platforms as sources of information Utilizing what is available in an environment especially the modern inventions Accessing the internet to search for additional information to better understand a concept Considering online platforms to be enlightened on a certain topic Using the internet as a source of information i through youtube videos related to language Exploring websites and movies relevant to language learning Considering technology as best resources due to its accessibility and ease of use	Technological Support through Internet	Utilization of Credible Varied Resources	Constructivism Theory
	Sourcing out books, newspapers, cellphone and internet in bridging the gap in learning Opting to use additional books that can be found at home to cope the challenges	Conventional Information Resources		

in language learning
Having additional language sources
such as textbooks
Having the library as one of the
resources

Utilizing Research Skills with Technological Intervention. The students shared their coping mechanism regarding how they manage to demonstrate taking the initiative to self-directed learning by leveraging online resources and technology. They engage in independent study by conducting targeted online searches, utilizing language-learning applications and exploring various technological interventions to enhance their language proficiency. Through these strategies students are able to take an autonomous and resourceful approach to mastering a new language, utilizing the availability and accessibility of modern technology and digital learning tools.

Searching through Online and Library. This is the first code for the first probed issue. When students are having difficulties in understanding the concept of a particular topic, seeking assistance through online platform and utilizing libraries can be beneficial. These platforms offer a wide range of courses and tutorials on various subjects, which can help students to understand the topic from a different perspective or in a more engaging way.

Similarly, challenges in instructional effectiveness, particularly in their coursework as English major students, involve utilizing online resources such as YouTube videos and podcasts featuring proficient English speakers. By actively listening to and observing how English is constructed and spoken in these digital platforms, they supplement their learning and teaching techniques. By using these techniques, they are able to enhance and expand their understanding of the language, significantly contributing to the absorption of learnings related language. As Participant 1 said that:

“I use my coping strategies to handle the challenges in instruction effectiveness especially among subject nga purcom. My coping strategies is kanang mutan’aw kog mga online gud nga mga speakers nga maaccess nako sa youtube or sa podcast, ginapaminaw nako unsaon ang pagka construct in English kay basically English man juy ginakuan as English major, so, akong coping mecahanism lang guro or strategies is mutan’aw sa internet as a reference sa akong English learning”. (IDI-01)

(I use specific coping strategies to address challenges in instructional effectiveness, especially in my major subject, which is purposive communication. My coping mechanism involves watching online videos of proficient speakers on platforms like YouTube or podcasts. I listen to and analyze English language constructs because English is the language used in my field of study as an English major. Therefore, my coping strategy is to use the internet as a reference for my English learning.)

Moreover, when facing difficulties, students actively seek additional information online to enhance their understanding and skills. This proactive approach involves exploring various online platforms and resources, such as educational websites, video tutorials, and interactive forums. By searching for explanations, supplementary materials, and practical examples, students can gain deeper insights and overcome obstacles in their learning process, significantly contributing to the students’ language learning journey. As what Participant 4 stated that:

“Sa mga resources is internet. Kanang maglisod ko’g cope up sa challenges when it comes to language learning so ga search pud ko og kanang mga additional info sa internet. Also, daghan man mig libro sa balay. So, kana pud is mga additional textbooks. Mao pud gyud na akong ginagamit to cope with challenges related to language learning.” (IDI-04)

(I rely on the internet when I encounter difficulties or challenges in language learning. I search for additional information online to help me cope with these challenges. It is not just the internet; we also have many books at home. I use additional textbooks to address challenges related to language learning.)

Additionally, the participant emphasized the value of the library as a crucial resource for accessing information and a tool that helps students cope with difficulties and challenges in language learning. Libraries provide a wealth of materials, such as books, journals, and digital resources, which can support students in overcoming obstacles and enhancing their skills. By offering a dedicated space for study and research, libraries play a significant role in maintaining students' interest and motivation in language learning, pushing learners to become more willfull to learn as they can access various resources or materials. With this, she stated that:

“So, my support resources nu is kanang library kay pag dili nako ma or if maka face ka og mga challenges, muadto ka og library para ma cope tu sya nako nga challenges. Also, agree ko sa uban na mga answer na magseek og supports sa friends and family. Yes, that’s all.” (FGD-04).

(My support resources include the library. When facing challenges that I do not know how to handle, I go to the library to address those challenges. I also agree with others who seek support from friends and family. That is all.)

Utilizing Apps and Website. This is the second code for the first probe issue. Using applications and online platforms offers a convenient and varied method for improving learning experience. These online platforms allow for convenient access to educational materials at all times and locations, accommodating different learning preferences through engaging lessons, videos, quizzes, and games. Integrating these tools into a comprehensive learning strategy, students can enhance language learning.

With regards to that, student often describes their practice of seeking out websites or platforms to enhance their language skills, particularly in using English. They believed that by actively seeking out specific websites or online platforms, it will help them enhance their language skill development, specifically focusing on improving and maintaining their English language interest. Utilizing this strategy allows them to better explore and come up with various and effective tools in enhancing and harnessing their language skills. As Participant 7 said that:

"Sometimes I seek a website or platform to enhance my language skills, especially in using English. There's a website, ako syang ginagamit sa una. It allows me to practice speaking, and the AI corrects my pronunciation and usage of words. I also used to write randomly and read it. Sometimes, I would just talk, and the AI would auto-type and correct any mistakes." (IDI-07)

(Sometimes, I look for a website or platform where I can improve my language skills, especially in using English. There is a website whose name I have forgotten, but I used it before for interactive storytelling, where an AI corrected pronunciation and word usage. I also used to write randomly and then read aloud. Sometimes, I simply talk or tell stories, and the AI autotypes and corrects any mistakes.)

Moreover, when encountering teachers of varying effectiveness, students maintain their interest in language learning by actively seeking supplementary resources. They turn to language apps and online tutorials on platforms like YouTube to enhance their understanding and skills. This approach allows them to supplement their classroom learning with additional explanations and practice, helping to overcome any gaps or challenges. By leveraging these resources, students can continue to engage with the language and stay motivated, ensuring their learning progress remains steady despite inconsistencies in instructional quality. As what FGD-01 said:

"Okay nu, so, when faced with teachers of varying effectiveness, I maintain my interest in language by seeking out additional resources like language app, and also, I search on YouTube---online tutorials and immerse myself with my peers who can help me address, understand the lesson well." (FGD-01)

(When confronted with teachers of different effectiveness levels, I keep my interest in language alive by seeking additional resources such as language apps and online tutorials on platforms like YouTube. I also engage with peers who can assist in addressing and understanding the lessons better.)

In addition, they utilize various technological interventions, such as language learning applications like Duolingo, to rekindle their interest in language education. By leveraging these tools, students can sustain their enthusiasm for language learning, even when faced with teachers whose methods may not perfectly align with their personal learning styles. These digital resources provide interactive and engaging ways to practice and improve language skills, offering a tailored learning experience that helps students stay motivated and make continuous progress.

"Personally, as a future educator I am aware that there is no teaching method that is one size fits all so I make use of various technological intervention such as applications sa language learning. For instance kay katong nga application duo lingo which is very helpful to rekindle my interest to language learning. Through that technological interventions, I keep my interest in language education when dealing with a teacher whose methods may not match my learning style." (FGD-03)

(Personally, as a future educator, I am aware that there is no teaching method that fits all situations. Therefore, I utilize various technological interventions, such as language learning applications. For instance, the application Duolingo is very helpful in rekindling my interest in language learning. Additionally, through these technological interventions, I maintain my interest in language education, even when dealing with a teacher whose methods may not match my learning style.)

Establishing Social Support Network. Many of the participants shared their strategies with regards to collaborative approach to learning by actively seeking assistance and sharing ideas with friends to better understand language concepts and stay engaged in language learning. This approach not only fosters a supportive learning environment but also encourages mutual learning and knowledge-sharing among peers. By leveraging the insights and perspectives of their friends, students enriches their language learning experience and strengthens their comprehension of language concepts through collaborative efforts.

Supportive Friends. This is the third code for the first probe issue. The students adopted a collaborative learning approach by actively seeking assistance and sharing ideas with friends to enhance their understanding and maintain interest in language learning. They rely on their friends' support and insights to grasp challenging concepts and stay engaged with the language. Additionally, this collaborative effort not only strengthens their understanding of language concepts but also fosters a sense of motivation to continuously improve their language proficiency with the help of their friends.

In connection, many of the participants emphasized that friends play a crucial role in keeping their interest alive in language learning by helping them cope with the challenges and providing support with regards in language learning. Through their friends' assistance and engagement, the individual remains motivated and enthusiastic about language learning, demonstrating the importance of peer collaboration and support in their educational journey. As Participant 4 stated that:

"Siguro sir is siguro ang ano pud factor nga daghan kag friends kay sila man jud tung mga tao gyud nga akong ginaduolan when it comes na kanang kintahay maglisod kog sabot so sila pud siguro ang rason sir nganong ay sila pud siguro ang rason or through sa ilaha

po sir is na keep gihapon akong interest when it comes to language learning.” (IDI-04).

(One significant factor could be having many friends, as they are the individuals an individual often turns to when encountering difficulties in understanding certain concepts. Friends likely play a crucial role in maintaining an individual's interest in language learning by assisting and providing support when needed. Through their friends' involvement, an individual's enthusiasm for language learning is sustained, highlighting the importance of peer engagement in their educational journey.)

Additionally, Participant 6 also recognized that seeking help or assistance from friends will lead to collaborative learning where students adapt and collaborate with their friends will have a better understanding about the language concepts or ideas. Hence, this collaborative effort involves reaching out to friends for support and working together to deepen comprehension and learning of the language. Individuals whom one can reach out with when having hard times or difficulties in grasping confusing concepts could positively impact language learning. She added that:

“Also ang isa pud ka factor sir is katong mangayog tabang or assistance sa imong kuan isig ka—imong friends. Mura japon syag ma kuan sir mura japon syag mapadulong sya sa collaborative nga kuan paagi mu-adapt or magpatabang sa imong mga friends para mas masabtan pa jud ang concept or idea sa pag learn sa language.” (IDI-04)

(Another factor is seeking help or assistance from your friends. It seems that this approach is still effective, as it allows you to adapt and rely on your friends to better understand the concepts or ideas involved in learning a language through a collaborative method.)

Moreover, seeking assistance and sharing ideas with friends as part of their language learning process involves actively engaging with peers to clarify doubts, exchange insights, and collaborate on understanding language concepts. With that, by seeking assistance from friends, the students created a supportive learning environment where they can benefit from diverse perspectives and collective knowledge. As FGD-02 stated that:

“By asking pud sakoang mga friends kung nasabtan ba tu nila mao na sya ang kanang unsay tawag ani kanang methods na nga akong ginabuhap para mao tu ma keep nako ang kuan interest sa pag learn og language.” (FGD-02)

(By asking my friends if they understand certain topics, this is the method I use to maintain my interest in language learning.)

In addition, FGD-04 emphasized that seeking assistance from friends is beneficial, as they can offer valuable support and insights. Collaborative learning with peers allows students to delve deeper into their studies, expand their understanding, and gather additional resources. This approach not only enriches the learning experience but also fosters a supportive learning environment where students can share knowledge and strategies, obtaining ideas from different perspectives. He additionally stated that:

“So, ako pud sir, in addition, seeking assistance sakong friends is one good thing sir. And, isa pud ana sir is we have library so of course makatabang sya sa atoa nga mas ma develop o maexplore pa nato ang murag needs, especially sa mga lessons and topics nga related sa every subject po.” (FGD-04)

(In addition to seeking assistance from my friends, which is a beneficial way for us to share ideas, another advantage is having access to our library. This resource helps us further develop and explore areas of interest, especially in lessons and topics related to every subject.)

Teacher's Assistance. This is the fourth code for the first probe issue. Teachers have expertise and training that enable them to explain concepts, clarify doubts, and provide guidance to students. Seeking help from teachers allows us to gain deeper insights, correct misunderstandings, and improve our understanding of the material. Teachers also serve as mentors and role models, offering support and encouragement to students in their learning journey.

In that sense, teachers play a crucial role in helping students overcome challenges by offering clear explanations, providing additional resources, and delivering personalized support. Their guidance helps students navigate difficulties and improve their understanding of the material. Beyond direct instruction, teachers also serve as mentors and role models, fostering a positive learning environment that motivates students to strive for academic success especially boosting their interest in learning the language and work for the goals and desires they have in life. As Participant 3 said that:

“Ask for help, for example pareha sakoa, I know a teacher since my elementary nga kanang kabalo or kanang pwede gud nako maaskan og help, so mangu—nag-ask ko sa iya if “ma'am, pwede ba nako ni iask sa imoha nga question kay wala nako nasabtan ato nga teacher. So, sa imoha ko mag ask unsa imong perception, unsa imong ideas about ani? (IDI-03)

(I seek help from teachers, such as one I have known since elementary school whom I trust to provide assistance. I approach them and politely ask, 'Ma'am, may I ask you a question because I did not understand it from the other teacher? What is your perception or idea about this?' This is how I seek their help.)

Challenging Linguistic Material. In the context of teacher effectiveness and language interest, teachers play a critical role in breaking down difficult linguistic concepts into digestible segments, employing engaging instructional methods, and providing additional resources to spark curiosity and sustain motivation among students. Effective teachers understand the importance of adapting teaching strategies to cater to diverse learning needs, ensuring that challenging material is presented in a way that fosters understanding and

enthusiasm for language learning. By addressing challenging linguistic material effectively, teachers can cultivate a positive learning environment where students feel supported, encouraged, and motivated to explore and master complex language concepts.

Encountering Unfamiliar Vocabulary. This is the first code for the second probe issue. Participants stated that they experienced challenges encountering unfamiliar words that is being utilized by the teacher, this will lead to have difficulties in terms of understanding the concept or topic.

In connection with that, students believes that the need for assistance, such as using a dictionary to understand unfamiliar words, emphasize the importance of integrating internet resources into language learning. When encountering words that are new or unfamiliar, students practice integrating internet resources like dictionaries into their learning process, hence, students demonstrated a resourceful strategy to enhance language skills and overcome obstacles independently. As Participant 1 stated that:

“Kanang manginahanglan nakog assistance just like na naay mga words nga dili nako masabta, kinahanglan na nakog assistance just like mga dictionary—kinahangalan na nakog dictionary kay ang words bag’o pa sakoa. Mag inquire ko sa mga dictionary or di kaha online—ma-integrate pud nako ang internet.” (IDI-01)

(When I need assistance, especially with unfamiliar words that I do not understand, I rely on resources like dictionaries, particularly online dictionaries, because these words are new to me. That is why I use the internet to inquire and integrate dictionary searches into my learning process.)

Further, experiencing a sense of being left behind due to difficulty in understanding highfalutin words is a common challenge among students. When faced with complex language that exceeds their current comprehension level, students often struggle to keep up with the material. This feeling of being overwhelmed can hinder their ability to fully grasp and engage with the content, leading to frustration and a diminished confidence in their language skills. Addressing this issue involves providing clearer explanations and more accessible language to support students in overcoming these obstacles and enhancing their understanding. Participant 4 stated that:

"When I feel hopeless nako, kana nga moments nga marealize nako nga ‘dili nako kaya,’ dira gyud na ko magkinahanglan ug assistance, labi na if ma-feel nako nga ma-left behind ko kung dili ko makasabot sa concept nga gina-tudlo. Usahay pud, kung maglisod ko sabot sa concepts, especially sa English, dira nako mag-apply sa akong mga coping strategies." (IDI-04)

(During those times when I feel really hopeless, I realize that I cannot handle this. It is precisely at those moments that I need assistance, especially if I feel left behind when I cannot grasp the concept being taught. Additionally, when I struggle, particularly with understanding concepts in English, I find it difficult to comprehend. During these times, I apply my coping strategies.)

Confronting Difficult Material. This is the second code for the second probe issue. Facing challenging material may seem overwhelming and difficult, especially when it surpasses one's current understanding. Students may become overwhelmed and unsure about what steps to take when dealing with complex or advanced topics that are hard to understand.

In connection with that, feelings of incompetence and annoyance, especially when trying to grasp ideas that seem beyond their abilities, are common among students. It is essential to employ effective learning techniques and seek appropriate assistance or materials. Utilizing strategies such as breaking down complex concepts into manageable parts, using visual aids, or accessing supplementary resources can help clarify difficult content. This allows the learner to simplify difficult concepts and concretize their understanding by employing the mentioned strategy or source of assistance. As what Participant 2 said that:

"Kanang dili gud swak ang akong learning method sa akong teachers. During those times, I had to find ways to help and cope with the challenges on my own. Dili tungod kay dili sila kabalo mutudlo, pero lahi lang jud kog space to learn. So, I really had to rely on myself to handle those challenges." (IDI-02)

(During those times, my learning methods did not align with my teachers' strategies. I had to find ways to help and cope with the challenges on my own. It was not that my teachers did not know how to teach; it was just that I needed a different space to learn. So, I really had to rely on myself to handle those challenges.)

Stress Management Techniques. In context of teacher’s effectiveness and language interest, Stress management techniques, such as mindfulness and meditation, can enhance teachers' effectiveness and language interest by reducing stress, improving focus, creativity, and problem-solving abilities, and promoting a positive learning environment. By managing stress, teachers can foster a more positive attitude towards their work and increase motivation and enthusiasm for teaching, leading to a more engaging and productive language learning experience for students.

Optimism. This is the first code for the third probe issue. A positive and hopeful attitude towards teaching and learning a language reflects a belief in students' potential for growth and development. It signifies a strong commitment to fostering a supportive learning environment. Educators embody this mindset by anticipating favorable outcomes for their students, encouraging innovative teaching strategies and resilience in overcoming challenges.

In that sense, students understand that feeling frustrated at a moment doesn’t define their outlook for the next day. Instead of letting frustration dictate their mindset, they stay committed to their studies and maintain hope in their ability to overcome challenges. This

resilient attitude allows them to persist through difficulties, keeping their focus on long-term goals and continuing to make progress despite temporary setbacks. As what Participant 1 stated that:

"Kung naa koy frustrations, mag-divert lang ko sa akong atensyon sa optimism. Dili ko magpadala sa frustration, kay dili man kini magdugay. Kung frustrated ko, magtuon gihapon ko ug dili mawala ang paglaom. Dili ko gusto nga ang akong frustration magdala sa akong mood. Sa akong prinsipyo, dili kinahanglan mastress, mao nga wala kaayo ko nagpa-apekto sa frustration ug stress sa eskwela." (IDI-01)

(When I encounter frustrations, I simply divert my attention to optimism. I do not let frustration affect me for long. When I feel frustrated, I continue to study and do not lose hope. I do not want my frustration to dictate my mood because I enjoy my life. According to my principles, there is no need to be stressed, which is why I do not let frustration and stress impact my experience in school.)

Many of the participant believed that having an optimistic characteristic and maintaining a positive outlook in life involves consistently approaching situations with hope and resilience. It means seeing challenges as opportunities for growth rather than obstacles. When faced with difficulties, individuals with this trait tend to focus on solutions rather than dwelling on problems. As FGD-03 stated that:

"I manage stress or frustration when encountering a teacher whose approach may not immediately foster my language interest in the classroom through intrinsic motivation. So, when I say intrinsic motivation, I motivate myself, constantly remind myself about the benefits or the advantages that I can get if I strive harder for me to conquer the challenges brought by language learning." (FGD-03)

(I manage stress or frustration when encountering a teacher whose approach may not immediately foster my language interest in the classroom through intrinsic motivation. I motivate myself by constantly reminding myself about the benefits or advantages that I can gain if I strive harder and also overcome the challenges.)

Rest and Relaxation. This is the second code for the third probe issue. Rest and relaxation play a crucial role in enhancing teacher effectiveness and language interest by promoting overall well-being and reducing stress levels. Thus, prioritizing rest and relaxation, students as well as teachers can create a more positive and productive classroom environment, leading to improved academic outcomes.

In connection to that, many of the participant believe the importance of taking breaks and engaging in activities that bring stress relief and enjoyment when facing challenges or setbacks. These strategies allowed students for a temporary pause to recharge and reset before continuing with tasks or goals. Hence, finding ways to combine relaxation with learning, individuals can maintain motivation and resilience in pursuit of their learning goals. This will serve as the simplest yet the most effective strategy to revitalize one's strength to continue. As Participant 7 stated that:

"Sa reality, mag-stop ko usahay. Pag mahuwasan nako, magpadayon napud. Naa pud koy mga ways para ma-manage ang stress, sama sa mga hobbies like pagdula og online games o pagtan'aw og English movies. Bisan stress ko, maka-learn gihapon ko sa akong ginatan-aw. Usahay, maka-learn pud ko pinaagi sa pagbasa sa subtitles, kay hilig man ko magtan-aw og foreign language movies, sama sa Thai o Korean." (IDI-07)

(In reality, I sometimes stop. Once I feel better, I continue again. I also have ways to manage my stress, such as my hobbies like playing online games or watching English movies. Even when I am stressed, I still learn from what I watch. Sometimes, I also learn by reading subtitles because I enjoy watching foreign language movies, like Thai or Korean.)

Furthermore, Participant 1 recognizes the importance of seeking support and guidance from trusted family members or loved ones during times of frustration or difficulty. Building strong relationships with parents or guardians who can offer wise advice and comfort is invaluable for managing emotions and overcoming obstacles. This support provides not only practical solutions but also emotional reassurance, helping students to surpass challenges with greater resilience and confidence. With this, the learner tended to have hope and become motivated to learning language despite the difficulties and challenges faced because of the support received from the family members and friends. He stated that:

"Personally, kung frustrated nako, una gyud nakong duolan akong mama jud kay duol man ko sakong mama ba. That's why, those persons especially my mama will advise me nga "frustrated? Nak, mulabay ranang ing'ana nga mga butang. Mao nay coping mechanisms nako when in terms to—mangita kog...mu seek kog tabang sa usa ka person, ako jung mama." (IDI-01)

(Personnally, when I feel frustrated, my first approach is to open up to my mother because I am close to her, and also with my father. They guide me and give advice like, 'Do not dwell too much on those things when you're frustrated.' That is why they are my go-to people when I need help and guidance.)

In addition, FGD-04 also recognizes the importance of self-care and seeking support from friends and family during times of stress or frustration. The participant emphasizes the need to take breaks and prioritize personal relaxation to manage overwhelming feelings related to studying or learning. By incorporating self-care practices and relying on a supportive network, individuals can better cope with academic pressures and maintain a healthy balance. Rooting from experiences, a participant additionally stated that:

"In my case, sir, I manage stress and frustration by taking time to rest. Sometimes, frustration comes not just from studying but also from figuring out how to learn. It helps to bond with friends and family, as they allow us to relax and take a breather from our problems.

That is what I do." (FGD-04)

(In my case, I manage stress and frustration by taking time to rest. Sometimes, frustration arises not just from studying but also from figuring out how to learn. It helps to bond with friends and family, as they allow us to relax and take a break from our problems. That is what I do.)

Language Learning Motivation. In the context of teacher effectiveness and language interest, motivation is influenced by various factors, including the teacher's teaching style, the classroom environment, and the learner's individual differences. Teachers can enhance learners' motivation by creating a supportive and engaging learning environment, using effective teaching strategies, and fostering learners' autonomy, relevance, and relatedness to the holistic development of the students.

Intrinsic Motivation. This is the first code for the fourth probe issue. It is internal drive and personal satisfaction of the students experience when they engage in learning activities for their inherent enjoyment, interest, and value. It is characterized by a genuine desire to learn, explore, and understand without the need for external rewards or pressures. Therefore, intrinsically motivated students are more likely to be engaged, persistent, and successful in their learning, as they find the learning process enjoyable, challenging, and meaningful.

In connection with that, many of the participants highlights the importance of setting clear goals and focusing on progress to manage stress and frustration effectively. By reminding oneself of specific language learning objectives and tracking progress towards academic goals, individuals can maintain motivation and a sense of purpose amid challenges. As FGD-01 stated that:

"I am managing stress or frustration through reminding myself of my language learning goals and focusing on my progress as it will remind me of what objectives I really had in my academic goals. I also seek support from peers or mentors who can give me insights to cope with challenges." (FGD-01)

(I manage stress or frustration by reminding myself of my language learning goals and focusing on my progress. When I concentrate on my progress, it reminds me of the objectives I have set for my academic goals. Additionally, I seek support from peers or mentors who can provide insights on how to cope with them.)

Moreover, when students are encouraged to set their own goals, they are more likely to be invested in their learning and take responsibility for their progress. This sense of ownership fosters higher engagement and motivation, as students feel personally connected to their educational journey. Defining their own objectives which is to learn language, students can exert their efforts to meet their individual needs and interests, leading to more meaningful and effective language learning experiences. As FGD-03 said that:

"Sa akoang case nu kay if in'ani gud nga problems ang mag arise, ang akong ginabuhang lang is to remind myself about my goal nu, the same with what has what Ms had said earlier nu nga kanang iremind pud nako akong self nga kaning dili nga layo daghan pa kaayo kog things gani nga I need to learn so, with that, I'll have the motivation to learn more, not relying only with the teaching strategy but also to rely on my capabilities na I can do more without relying with others. Mao lang na po." (FGD-03)

(In my case, when such problems arise, what I do is remind myself of my goals, similar to what Ms. mentioned earlier about reminding myself that there are still many things I need to learn. With that mindset, I will have the motivation to learn more, not only relying on teaching strategies but also on my own capabilities, knowing that I can achieve more without depending on others. That's all.)

Additionally, intrinsically motivating oneself and constantly reminding oneself of the benefits and advantages of language learning play crucial roles in fostering a positive attitude. This self-motivation helps maintain interest in the language and sustains enthusiasm throughout the learning process. When students recognize the personal and practical rewards of language proficiency—such as improved communication skills, cultural insights, and career opportunities—they are more likely to stay committed. As FGD-06 said that:

"So, for me nu, I manage my stress or frustration when encountering a teacher's approach who may not immediately foster my language interest in the classroom is I go back questioning myself why did I start this journey. So, through that, akong ma realize sakong self nga 'ay, I am here kay naa koy goal, and that goal inspires me to continue or to pursue language learning. Also, I seek advices from my peers on dealing ahh this kind of problem and also my family pud nu, they also motivate me to continue." (FGD-06)

(For me, I manage my stress or frustration when encountering a teacher whose approach may not immediately foster my language interest in the classroom by reflecting on why I started this journey. Through this process, I remind myself and realize that I am here because I have a goal, and that goal inspires me to continue pursuing language learning. Additionally, I seek advice from my peers on how to deal with this kind of problem, and my family also motivates me to keep going.)

Extrinsic Motivation. This is the fourth code for the third probe issue. Driven by external rewards or consequences, it can be effective in getting students to complete tasks or behave in certain ways, but it may not lead to deep learning or sustained engagement in the long run. Hence, there are many factors that can support students' learning and motivation by creating a supportive environment, engaging learning experiences, goal setting, and displaying teacher enthusiasm to foster conducive teaching-learning atmosphere.

In connection to that, being motivated by goals and family as inspiration can be a powerful combination that drives individuals to

achieve success and fulfilment in various aspects of their lives. This means that students who are motivated by goals and family as inspiration can create a powerful driving force that propels you towards success while keeping your priorities aligned with what truly matters to you. This factor could greatly impact and push learners to really study and adhere to learning the language, equipping themselves with the necessary skills to become proficient or good in using a language. Upon having this experienced, Participant 4 openly shared that:

“Kanang stress, ang akong ginaduolan kay akoang family, akong mama, ug akong lover. Aside from them, I also have friends who understand me. Dili lang ako ang drained sa classroom; apil man pud akong mga classmates. Kung stress na jud ko, muduol ko nila, bisan stress sila. Nindot kaayo ang feeling nga dili lang ikaw ang stressed, kundi kamo tanan. Kana ang akong coping strategies para ma-manage ang stress. Gina-maintain pud nako ang optimistic characteristic, nga nag-hunahuna nga bisan stress kaayo, this too shall pass.” (IDI-04)

(When I feel stressed, I turn to my family, my mother, and my partner. Aside from them, I also have friends who understand me. I am not the only one who feels drained in the classroom; my classmates feel it too. When I am really stressed, I approach them, even if they are stressed as well. It feels good to know that I am not the only one feeling this way. These are my coping strategies for managing stress. I also maintain an optimistic outlook, reminding myself that even when it is very stressful, this too shall pass.)

In addition, many of the participant highlights that encouragement and support have played a crucial role in shaping academic and personal growth. Through experiences and achievements, students inspired to strive for excellence and expand knowledge in various fields. Collaborative learning sessions helped the students to deepened understanding not just a particular concept or subjects but also fostered a sense of accountability in one’s learning, upholding the importance and crucial role of cooperative and group-based learning. As Participant 5 said that:

“Siguro, sir, how I manage that stress is that—I really seek help to my friends and even the instructors themselves pero pag once naman busy ang instructor, I would go for other social media platform like online platform na could help me like you tube wherein I could search for how to understand or how to kanang make me understand ba kung unsa ba ang pasabot ana or unsa bay kailangan nako buhaton para masabtan ko tu nga specific nga task or specific nga topic po.” (IDI-05)

(Perhaps, sir, I manage stress by seeking help from my friends and even the instructors themselves. However, if the instructor is busy, I turn to other social media platforms, such as YouTube, where I can search for information on how to understand or comprehend the specific task or topic I am dealing with.)

Utilization of Credible Varied Resources. In the context of teacher effectiveness and language interest utilization of credible varied resources refers to the importance of using diverse, high-quality resources to support teaching and learning. This includes utilizing a range of instructional materials, such as textbooks, charts, and other educational technology, as well as incorporating different teaching methods and strategies.

Social Support. This is the first code for the fourth probe issue. A strong support system is essential for successful language learning, including family, friends, and knowledgeable teachers. Seeking advice and feedback from instructors and practicing with supportive friends can enhance language skills and motivation. Utilizing these resources can create a conducive environment for language learning and lead to greater proficiency.

In connection, having a strong support system and utilizing resources can effectively overcome challenges in learning. Many of the participants highlight the role of supportive peers who encourage and motivate them to keep studying even when they face difficulties with certain teachers or subjects. This emphasizes the significance of surrounding oneself with like-minded individuals who share a passion for learning and can provide encouragement during tough times. This is evident as Participant 2 stated that:

"I'm lucky to have a strong support system with peers who are driven to learn. There are times when I don't feel a connection with the teacher, but my peers encourage me to study together. For resources, I rely on the internet and our library when the teacher's instruction isn't clear. It's really about my peers and my initiative to seek out information online. I try to tackle the challenges I face during that time." (IDI-02)

(I am lucky to have a strong support system with peers who are motivated to learn. There are times when I do not feel a connection with the teacher, but my peers encourage me to study together. For resources, I rely on the internet and our library when the teacher’s instruction is unclear. It is really about my peers and my initiative to seek out information online. I try to tackle the challenges I face during that time.)

Moreover, friends play a crucial role as a backbone in the learning process, highlighting the significant impact of supportive friendships on students' success. Seeking support from friends who are willing to assist and encourage can greatly enhance motivation and resilience in pursuing educational goals. These friendships provide emotional support, practical help, and encouragement, which are essential for overcoming challenges and maintaining a positive outlook. Participant 5 said that:

“As what I have mentioned earlier, I would say na really friends gyud since sila ang backbone sa akong learning wherein they could really help. I would really say na I am blessed beyond measure to my friends na really helpful when it comes to my success in my

learning endeavor and to all success nga akong na attain”. (IDI-05)

(As I mentioned earlier, I would say that my friends are like the backbone of my learning, as they truly help me. I can honestly say that I am blessed beyond measure to have friends who are so supportive in my learning endeavors and to all success I have achieved)

Furthermore, seeking assistance, support, and guidance from friends in learning a new language can be incredibly beneficial. Not only does it provide a sense of motivation, but it also offers the opportunity for interactive practice, feedback, and cultural insights that can enhance students’ language learning experience. Engaging with friends who are fluent or also learning the language can create a supportive environment where students can exchange knowledge, correct each other’s mistakes, and celebrate progress together, making the learning process more enjoyable and effective. As FGD-04 said that:

“I seek support with my peers since they’re the ones nga naa sa akoang side kay same man mi—sila ang saksi sakoang educational journey kay sila man akong kauban sa classroom and with that, makarealize ko nu nga through their motivation sakoang kay makahatag syag drive to strive harder when it comes to language education especially if I do know nga they are also going through something nga the same sakoang”. (FGD-03)

(I seek support from my peers because they are the ones who are by my side throughout our educational journey since we are together in the classroom. With that, I realize that through their motivation, they can give me the drive to strive harder when it comes to language education, especially knowing that they are also experiencing similar to mine)

Similarly, FGD-04 recognizes that having friends and family to keep you motivated in learning a new language can be a powerful driving force. Their encouragement and support play a crucial role in maintaining enthusiasm and commitment, especially during challenges or setbacks. This support helps sustain motivation and provides reassurance, making it easier to manage obstacles and stay focused on language learning goals. With this, the importance of having friends is irrefragably play a crucial role in language learning process. As FGD 4 said that:

“In my case, my support systems nu is akong friends, aside that I love them, ga seek sad kog advices sa ilaha--sakong language learning kay sila man akoang permi kauban. Sa school, sila akong kauban. Wala koy laing ma seekan og assistance or advices with regards sa mga challenges so sa ilaha ko mu tap, either, online ba or sa face to face.” (FGD-04)

(In my case, my main support system is definitely my friends. Aside from loving them, I also seek advice from them regarding my language learning because they are my constant companions. At school, they are always with me, so I do not need to seek assistance or advice elsewhere regarding my challenges; I turn to them, whether online or face-to-face.)

Additionally, having a knowledgeable teacher is essential because they possess the expertise to effectively convey information, provide valuable guidance, and inspire students to reach their full potential. Their deep understanding of the subject matter enables them to teach concepts clearly and address individual learning needs. A knowledgeable teacher can motivate and engage students, fostering a positive learning environment that encourages exploration and growth. With this, teachers’ vast and deep understanding to a certain concept greatly impacts students’ learning and development. As IDI-03 stated that:

“Mag ask kog help sa mga teachers kay basically sila ang equipped og knowledge, who at the same time maka ignite og interest ang ka broad sa ilang kahibalo nga itudlo sa students in learning. Or, if unavailable, we may opt to seek someone nga knowledgeable nga available na pwede nimo pangutan-an asking help from someone nga naay vast knowledge would really help boost our interest gyud.” (IDI-03)

(I ask for help from teachers because they are equipped with knowledge and can ignite interest through their broad understanding that they share with students. If they are unavailable, we might seek someone else who is knowledgeable and available to ask questions. Requesting help from someone with extensive knowledge can really boost our interest.)

Technological Support through Internet. This is last code for the fourth probe issue. The Internet has become an indispensable tool for communication, education, and commerce in the modern world. Moreover, technology has enabled students to access information from a broader variety of resources. Thanks to the internet, students now have the ability to obtain lectures, videos, and other educational resources from renowned experts and institutions worldwide, enabling students to gain knowledge from a variety of viewpoints and backgrounds.

Similarly, having technology, internet, and online platforms as sources of information is essential for modern education. They provide access to a wide range of resources, including educational videos, tutorials, interactive applications, and digital libraries. The internet enables learners to explore diverse perspectives, access real-time information, and engage in global communities, contributing to a more meaningful learning. As Participant 4 stated that:

“Dako jud kaayog tabang sir ang internet. Isa sya sa mga sources nga ikaw as English student or kanang language learning student, daghan jud kag makat’onan sa kuan especially in you tube, kanang mga videos. Mao man tu sya sir nu katong first is mag adto ko sa online platform second is friends. Also, sir, mag seek pud kog kuan sir advice from our—satoang instructors—mga teachers kay isa man gud pud sila sir nga makapag hatag satoa og idea para mas mulambo gud atoang kuan sir pag learn sa language.” (IDI-04)

(The internet is very helpful, sir, because it is a valuable resource for English or language learning students. Platforms like YouTube offer educational videos that can be very informative. So, my first step is to go to online platforms; the second is to turn to my friends. Additionally, I seek advice from our instructors or teachers, as they can provide us with important ideas)

Moreover, the importance of seeking diverse sources of support and resources to overcome challenges in language learning contributorily impact the learnings of the students. Many participants highlighted the value of utilizing online language communities, textbooks, and online courses as additional tools to supplement traditional classroom instruction and address gaps in teacher effectiveness. These sources allow learners to explore and meet diverse perspectives that would eventually concretize and strengthen their understanding towards concepts related to language learning. As FGD-01 stated that:

“We are facing lot of challenges in learning the language, and to cope with challenges related to teacher effectiveness, I seek support from online language communities and other language resources such as textbooks and online courses.” (FGD-01)

(We face many challenges when it comes to learning the language. To cope with challenges related to teacher effectiveness, I seek support from online language communities and use additional language resources such as textbooks and online courses.)

Data Integration of the Salient Quantitative and Qualitative Findings

The presented study on the interplay of Teacher Effectiveness and Language Interest among English Teacher Education students in the local college carried out a mixed method approach employing convergent parallel approach. The fifth research question of the study involved the corroboration of the findings from the quantitative and qualitative phase. The table 4 on the salient quantitative and qualitative findings presented the focal points of the study followed by the quantitative and qualitative findings in the second and third column. The findings from the qualitative findings which displayed the identified responses showed confirmation or disconfirmation to the quantitative results. The fourth column was the nature of the data integration and the fifth column contains the axiological implication based on the data describe in preceding columns.

Table 4.2. Joint Display of Salient Quantitative and Qualitative Findings

Aspect Or Focal Point	Quantitative Findings	Qualitative Findings	Nature Of Data Integration	Axiological Implications
Teacher Effectiveness	From Table 2.1 under the indicator subject matter knowledge with an overall mean of 4.17 specifically item number 5- relating the content to real-life situations by making the lessons more relevant and applicable to our daily lives (M= 4.22), are all rated as high.	On table 3.2 under the category real-life language application specifically in core idea 3 using real-life situations to connect lessons to everyday living.	Merging – converging	The integration of quantitative and qualitative data emphasized the effectiveness of making lessons relevant to real-life situations, revealing the importance of using appropriate teaching materials and technology to meet modern educational needs. It highlighted the value of fostering a supportive environment for student improvement through ongoing assessment and positive feedback. Further, it prevailed the importance of clear and precise language instruction, reflecting the need for effective communication in teaching to enhance student understanding and success.
	From Table 2.1 under the indicator instructional planning and strategies with an overall mean of 4.29, rated as high specifically item number 4- using appropriate material, technology and resources while teaching (M=4.29), rated as very high.	On table 3.2 under the category technology integration specifically core idea 2 integrating technology in instruction for 21st century learners.	Merging-Converging	
	From table 2.1 under the indicator assessment with an overall mean of 4.14, rated as high specifically item 5 encouraging students to do better next time (M=4.33), rated as very high.	On table 3.2 under the category assessment and evaluating specifically core idea 1 conducting assessment and evaluation to be aware on what to change and enhance.	Merging-converging	
	From table 2.1 under the indicator learning environment with an overall mean 4.26, specifically item 2- emphasizing continuous improvement towards students’ achievement (M= 4.29), are all rated as very high	On table 3.2 under the core idea positive learning environment specifically core idea 4, creating a good and positive environment thru giving feedback in a friendly manner.	Merging-converging	
		On table 3.2 under the category clear language instruction, specifically	Merging-Converging	

Language Interest	<p>From table 2.2 under the indicator attention with an overall mean of 4.13 specifically item 2- learning English comfortably at home (M=4.00), are all rated high.</p>	<p>core idea 1 giving thorough information on techniques in constructing sentences</p>	Merging – converging	<p>The integration of high ratings for learning English comfortably at home with qualitative feedback on interactive dialogue revealed the importance of immersive and</p>
	<p>From table 2.2 under the indicator motivation with an overall mean of 4.11, specifically item 1- practicing a daily habit of reading English books to enhance language proficiency (M=4.06), are all rated as high.</p>	<p>On table 4.1 under the category hobbies specifically core idea 1, doing hobbies like playing online games and watching movies like Thai and Korean with English subtitles</p>	Merging-converging	<p>collaborative experiences for effective language acquisition. The combination of motivation from daily English reading and enjoyment from hobbies like online games and movies with English</p>
	<p>From table 2.2 under the indicator enjoyment with an overall mean of 3.95 specifically item 2- asking my friends happily about their favourite English literature (M=3.73), are all rated as high</p>	<p>On the table 4.1 under the category extrinsic motivation specifically core idea 2, having helped and influenced by friends to become motivated in learning</p>	Merging-Converging	<p>subtitles showed how integrating enjoyable activities can enhance engagement. Social interactions, such as discussing English literature with friends, also played a crucial role in</p>
	<p>From table 2.2 under the indicator perception with an overall mean of 4.06, specifically item 1- learning English despite its difficulty for numerous opportunities (M=4.08), are all rated as high.</p>	<p>On the table 4.1 under the category optimism specifically core idea 1, diverting the attention by optimistically perceive things and still learn and don't lose hope, enjoy life while learning instead.</p>	Merging-converging	<p>fostering motivation. Additionally, the willingness to tackle English challenges combined with an optimistic attitude demonstrated the</p>
	<p>From table 2.2 under the indicator activities with an overall mean of 4.19, specifically item 5- practicing language skills through role-playing when English is used (M=4.17), are all rated as high.</p>	<p>On the table 3.2 under the category interactive group-based activity specifically core idea 1, having activities like conversation or dialogue in English</p>	Merging-converging	<p>importance of resilience and positivity in learning. Lastly, engaging in role-playing and group-based activities emphasized the effectiveness of immersive, interactive approaches for developing language skills.</p>
Lived experiences of the students relative to the Effectiveness of Teachers in Boosting their Language Interest	<p>From the table 2.1 under the indicator assessment with an overall mean of 4.14 specifically item 1- conducting class tests to monitor students' performance regularly (M= 4.06), are all rated high.</p>	<p>On the table 3.2 under the essential theme teacher's teaching competence, particularly, in category of assessment and evaluation.</p>	Merging-converging	<p>The data prevailed the importance of effective teaching practices in fostering student engagement and interest. High ratings for regular assessments, creating a</p>
	<p>From table 2.1 under the indicator learning environment with an overall mean of 4.26 rated as very high, specifically item 1- creating a climate of mutual trust and respect in the classroom (M=4.23; high)</p>	<p>On table 3.2 under the essential theme engaging and vibrant learning environment, particularly in the category of positive learning environment.</p>	Merging-converging	<p>respectful classroom environment, and adapting lessons to students' needs emphasize the value of strong teaching competence and pedagogical</p>
	<p>From table 2.1 under the effective communication with an overall mean of 4.29 rated as very high, specifically item 2- explaining lessons according to the age and ability of the students. (M=4.12; high)</p>	<p>On table 3.2 under the essential theme teacher teaching competence, particularly in the category of pedagogical knowledge.</p>	Merging-converging	<p>knowledge. Moreover, the importance of understanding students' perspectives and using diverse teaching strategies to enhance learning was emphasized, reflecting the</p>
	<p>From table 2.1 under the effective communication with an overall</p>	<p>On the table 3.2 under the essential theme mastery in</p>	Merging-converging	<p>need for interactive and engaging instructional</p>

	mean of 44.29, specifically item 5- listening students' perspectives about their struggles with learning (M=4.27), are all rated as very high.	instructional and content delivery, particularly in the category of teaching strategies.		methods.
	From table 2.1 under indicator instructional planning and strategies with an overall mean of 4.19, rated as very high specifically item 1- using different teaching strategies to enhance students' understanding (4.22; high).	On the table 3.2 under the essential theme engaging and vibrant learning environment particularly in the category of interactive group-based activities.	Merging-converging	
Ways of Handling Challenges and Maintaining Interest in Language Learning on the Varying Levels of Teachers' Effectiveness	From table 2.2 under the indicator of enjoyment with an overall mean of 3.95, specifically item 4- feeling fulfilled when reading English short stories and poems (4.07), are all rated as high.	On the table 4.1 under the essential theme utilizing research skills with technological intervention, particularly in the category of searching through online and library	Merging-converging	The data revealed that high ratings for feeling fulfilled when reading English short stories and poems align with the importance of utilizing research skills and technology to maintain interest and address challenges in language learning. High ratings for seeking ways to learn English for personal goals reflect the significance of credible resources and social support in achieving language acquisition. In addition, the value of intrinsic motivation was emphasized by high ratings for engaging with educational materials, while the effectiveness of combining collaborative group activities with reliable resources was highlighted for enhancing language learning experiences.
	From table 2.2 under the indicator perception with an overall mean of 4.06, specifically item 2- seeking ways to learn English to achieve my goals (M=4.20), are all rated as high.	On the table 4.1 under the essential theme utilization of credible varied resources particularly in the category social support.	Merging-converging	
	From table 2.2 under the indicator motivation with an overall mean of 4.13, specifically item 5- reading educational materials in English for comprehensive understanding (M=4.15), are all rated as high.	On the table 4.1 under the essential theme language learning motivation particularly on the category of intrinsic motivation	Merging-converging	
	From table 2.2 under the indicator activities with an overall mean of 4.19, specifically item 3- acquiring English skills through collaborative group activities (M=4.16) are all rated high.	On the table 4.1 under the essential theme utilization of credible varied resources particularly under the category of conventional information resources.	Merging-converging	

Teacher Effectiveness

In the quantitative phase under the indicator subject-matter knowledge, the specific item was rated high by the participants as relating the content to real-life situations by making the lessons more relevant and applicable to our daily lives.

The result is connected with the qualitative findings, which categorize as real-life language application specifically, core idea 3, using real-life situations to connect lessons to everyday living. Moreover, merging quantitative and qualitative data highlights the importance of connecting subject knowledge to real-life scenarios for effective language learning in daily life. Therefore, it is safe then to say that the quantitative results merged the qualitative results.

In the quantitative phase under the indicator instructional planning and strategies. Using appropriate material, technology and resources while teaching item was rated by the participant as high. The result is connected with the qualitative findings, which was categorized as technology integration, specifically core idea 2, integrating technology in instruction for 21st century learners. Merging quantitative and qualitative data emphasizes the necessity of applying subject knowledge in practical, everyday language learning contexts. It is safe then to say that quantitative and qualitative results merge.

In the quantitative phase under the indicator assessment, rated as high by the respondent specifically item number 5 - encouraging students to do better next time. This result was connected with the qualitative findings particularly categorized as assessment and evaluating, under core idea 1, conducting assessment and evaluation to be aware on what to change and enhance. Hence, fostering a supportive educational environment, integrating quantitative encouragement for student improvement with qualitative assessment-driven enhancements, prioritizes continual growth and development. Therefore, qualitative merges with the qualitative results.

In the quantitative phase under the indicator learning environment, rated as very high by the respondent specifically item number 2 -

emphasizing continuous improvement towards students' achievement. This result is connected with the qualitative findings particularly categorize as, positive learning environment, under the core idea 4, creating a good and positive environment thru giving feedback in a friendly manner. With that, highlighting the importance of nurturing supportive and growth-oriented atmospheres, the convergence of high quantitative ratings on student achievement improvement, coupled with qualitative emphasis on friendly feedback and positive learning environments, emphasize the value of fostering student success and well-being. It concludes that quantitative and qualitative results merges.

In the quantitative phase under the indicator effective communication, rated as very high by the participants specifically item number 1 - using correct vocabulary and grammar in teaching. This result is connected with the qualitative findings particularly categorized as clear language instruction, under core idea 1, giving thorough information on techniques in constructing sentences. In that sense, the combination of high quantitative ratings in communication skills with qualitative guidance on sentence construction highlights the importance of clear language instruction for effective teaching and understanding. Thus, this can be viewed that the quantitative and qualitative results merges.

Language Interest

In the quantitative phase under the indicator attention, rated as very high by the respondent, specifically item number 2 - learning English comfortably at home. This result is connected with the qualitative findings categorize as role-playing and dialogue under the core idea 3, using language by conversing or communicating with someone in English. In that sense, the merging of high interest in home-based English learning with interactive language use highlights the value of immersive experiences for fostering supportive language acquisition environments. This can be viewed that quantitative and qualitative finding merged.

In the quantitative phase under the indicator motivation, rated as high by the respondents, specifically item number 1 - practicing a daily habit of reading English books to enhance language proficiency. This is connected with the qualitative findings specifically categorize as hobbies, under core idea 1, doing hobbies like playing online games and watching movies like Thai and Korean with English subtitles. With that, the convergence of high motivation in daily English book reading with qualitative emphasis on incorporating hobbies like online gaming and watching movies with English subtitles underscores the value of integrating enjoyable activities to promote language acquisition and intrinsic interest in learning pursuits. This means that quantitative and qualitative findings merges.

In the quantitative phase under the indicator enjoyment, rated as very high by the respondents, specifically item number 2- asking my friends happily about their favourite English literature. This result is connected with the qualitative findings categorize as extrinsic motivation, specifically core idea 2, having helped and influence by friends to become motivated in learning. In connection to that, high quantitative ratings in enjoying English literature and seeking friends' recommendations, combined with qualitative emphasis on extrinsic motivation through social influences, highlight how social interactions foster motivation and engagement in learning. Thus, quantitative and qualitative results merges.

In the quantitative phase under the indicator perception, rated as high by the respondents specifically item number 1 - learning English despite its difficulty for numerous opportunities. This result is connected with the qualitative findings categorize as optimism under the core idea 1, diverting the attention by optimistically perceive things and still learn and don't lose hope, enjoy life while learning instead. Hence, high motivation from daily English book reading for language enhancement, coupled with incorporating hobbies like online gaming and watching Thai and Korean movies with English subtitles, emphasizes the value of integrating enjoyable activities to promote language acquisition and intrinsic interest in language learning pursuits. This can be viewed that quantitative merge with the qualitative result.

In the quantitative phase under the indicator activities, rated as high by the participants specifically item number 5 - practicing language skills through role-playing when English is used. This result is connected with the qualitative findings categorize as interactive group-activity, under the core idea 1, having activities like conversation or dialogue in English. In that sense, high quantitative ratings in engaging language activities like role-playing, along with qualitative emphasis on interactive group-based English conversations, underscore the effectiveness of immersive and collaborative learning for language skill development. This means that quantitative and qualitative result merges.

The Lived Experiences of the Students Relative to the Effectiveness of Teachers in Boosting their Language Interest

In the quantitative phase under the indicator assessment item number 1 - conducting class tests to monitor students' performance regularly was rated as high by the participants. This result is connected with the qualitative findings under the essential theme teacher's teaching competence, particularly under the category of assessment and evaluation. This highlights that, high teacher effectiveness ratings in conducting regular class tests to monitor student performance, combined with qualitative findings emphasizing teaching competence in assessment and evaluation, have meaningful implications for fostering student interest in language learning. This can be viewed that quantitative and qualitative result merges.

Moreover, in the quantitative phase under the indicator learning environment, was rated high by the participants, specifically item, creating a climate of mutual trust and respect in the classroom. This is in congruence with the qualitative findings which is under the

essential theme engaging and vibrant learning environment, specifically under code/category positive learning environment. This means that, high ratings for creating a climate of mutual trust and respect in the classroom align with qualitative findings emphasizing an engaging and vibrant learning environment, highlighting the importance of fostering a positive classroom atmosphere.

Furthermore, in the quantitative phase under the indicator, effective communication was rated high by the participants particularly item, explaining lessons according to the age and ability of the students. This was connected with the qualitative findings under the essential theme teacher teaching competence, specifically code/category pedagogical knowledge. This highlights that, high ratings for explaining lessons according to students' age and ability align with qualitative findings emphasizing teacher teaching competence, highlighting the importance of pedagogical knowledge for adapting instruction to meet diverse student needs effectively. Hence, quantitative and qualitative results merges.

Similarly, in the quantitative phase under the indicator effective communication, was rated very high by the participants specifically item, listening students' perspectives about their struggles with learning. This is in congruence with the qualitative findings under the essential theme mastery in instructional and content delivery, code/category of teaching strategies. The high rating of listening to students' perspectives about their learning struggles aligns with qualitative findings emphasizing mastery in instructional and content delivery, particularly emphasizing effective teaching strategies that prioritize understanding students' needs and challenges. This can be viewed that quantitative and qualitative results merges.

In addition, in the quantitative phase under the indicator instructional planning and strategies was rated by the participant as high specifically item number 1 - using different teaching strategies to enhance students' understanding. This result is connected to the qualitative findings under the essential theme engaging and vibrant learning environment, code/category of interactive group-based activities. High ratings for using varied teaching strategies to enhance understanding align with qualitative findings emphasizing engaging learning environments, particularly through interactive group activities that support effective instructional planning and implementation. This means that quantitative and qualitative results merges.

Ways of Handling Challenges and Maintaining Interest in Language Learning on the Varying Levels of Teachers' Effectiveness

In the quantitative phase under the indicator enjoyment was rated by the participant as high specifically item number 4 - feeling fulfilled when reading English short stories and poems. This is in congruence with the qualitative findings under the essential theme utilizing research skills with technological intervention, particularly in the category of searching through online and library. The high rating of enjoying English short stories and poems aligns with qualitative findings emphasizing research skills and technology use to sustain interest in language learning across different teaching levels. This can be viewed that quantitative and qualitative results merges.

Moreover, in the quantitative phase under the indicator perception was rated by the participant as high specifically item number 2 - seeking ways to learn English to achieve my goals. The result of the study is connected with the qualitative result under the essential theme utilization of credible varied resources, specifically code/category, social support. High ratings for pursuing English learning to achieve personal goals align with qualitative findings emphasizing diverse, credible resources and social support in language acquisition, underscoring the importance of networks and resources for goal-oriented learning. This emphasizes that quantitative and qualitative results merges.

Furthermore, under the indicator motivation was rated by the participants high specifically item number 2 - utilizing social media platforms as a means to learn and practice English. The result is connected language learning motivation particularly on the category of intrinsic motivation with the qualitative findings under the essential theme. High ratings for reading educational materials in English align with qualitative findings on language learning motivation, particularly intrinsic drive, emphasizing the importance of personal interest in enhancing language learning outcomes. This means that quantitative and qualitative results merges.

In addition, in the quantitative phase under the indicator activities was rated by the participant as high specifically item number 3 - acquiring English skills through collaborative group activities. This result is connected with the qualitative findings under the essential theme utilization of credible varied resources particularly under the category of conventional information resources. High ratings for English skill acquisition through group activities align with qualitative findings on using credible resources, emphasizing conventional information sources. This highlights the importance of combining interactive group activities with diverse sources for effective language learning. This can be viewed that quantitative and qualitative results merges.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

First, the status of teacher effectiveness was high in terms of subject matter knowledge, instructional planning and strategies, and assessment and on the other hand in terms of learning environment and effective communication was rated very high. And the status of language interest was also high in terms of attention, motivation, enjoyment, perception, and activities. Hence, this indicated that the indicators of teacher effectiveness and language interest were often manifested by English teacher education students.

Second, the findings revealed the significant relationship of teacher effectiveness and language interest among english teacher education students using mean, standard deviation and Pearson r. It was revealed that there is significant relationship between Teacher

Effectiveness and Language Interest.

Third, the thematic analysis of the qualitative data was done based from the responses gained through the conduct of in-depth interview (IDI) and focus group discussion (FGD). The results gave more information about the side of the participants in terms of their experiences relative to the effectiveness of teachers in boosting their language interest. Qualitatively, English teacher education students had been experiencing different situations which contributed to the way various factors affect their language interest. The following themes were emerged: linguistic and discourse competence issues, external and internal factors in language learning, mastery in instructional and content delivery, engaging and vibrant learning environment, group speaking activities, teacher's teaching competence.

Fourth, from the participants responses, other themes were identified which showed the coping mechanisms shared of English teacher education students with regards to ways of handling challenges and maintaining interest in language learning on the varying levels of teachers' effectiveness. The following were the themes: utilizing research skills with technological intervention, establishing social support network, challenging linguistic material, stress management techniques, language learning motivation, and utilization of credible varied resources.

Lastly, to better understand the impact of teacher effectiveness and language interest among English teacher education student, the responses were analyzed thematically to confirm the quantitative results of the study. Both the findings from the two phases were integrated based on the nature plan. The status of teacher effectiveness and language interest among English major students on the quantitative results showed that it converged to the data gained from the qualitative phase. Both of the quantitative and qualitative results confirmed that there was an interplay between teacher effectiveness and language interest.

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were being drawn:

To enhance the understanding of how teacher effectiveness influences language interest among students, the researcher recommended to conduct another study focusing on the same topic with a research title, "Exploring the Impact of Teacher Effectiveness on Language Interest Across All Majors in the Education Program in KCAST: A Mixed Method Study". This expanded research would include students from all education majors, providing a broader perspective beyond English majors. By utilizing a mixed-method approach, the study could collect both quantitative and qualitative data to gain deeper insights into the experiences and views of students across different majors. This would allow for a more comprehensive examination of how teaching strategies impact language engagement in diverse subjects such as mathematics, science, and social studies. The findings could inform more effective teaching practices that foster language interest across the entire education program. Since the status of the teacher effectiveness revealed that among the five indicators of teacher effectiveness, the assessment has the lowest mean which affected how students learn their lesson the least, it was recommended that educators should first prioritize the development and implementation of more effective assessment methods that accurately measure teacher effectiveness and positively influence student learning. This could involve exploring alternative assessment tools, refining existing ones, or incorporating multiple measures to provide a more comprehensive view of teacher performance. Through prioritizing the development of effective assessment methods, providing targeted professional development, considering the specific contexts in which teachers work, and maintaining a clear distinction between performance and effectiveness, educators can improve teacher effectiveness and positively impact student learning.

Further, language interest revealed that among the five indicators of language interest, the enjoyment had the lowest mean which affected how students stay engaged deeply in their interest in learning language, it was recommended that educators should focus on enhancing the enjoyment factor in language learning to deepen student engagement. Educators should incorporate interactive and engaging activities, such as games, discussions, and real-life applications, to make language learning enjoyable and meaningful for students. Additionally, creating a positive and supportive learning environment, encouraging student participation, and providing opportunities for self-expression can further boost student interest and motivation in language learning, fostering a deeper and more sustained engagement with the subject.

Based on the findings of the study, several recommendations were made to enhance teacher effectiveness and increase the language interest of English teacher education students. These recommendations focused on fostering self-directed learning, facilitating peer collaboration, offering personalized support, integrating technology, and making language learning more relevant through real-world applications.

Moreover, teachers were encouraged to actively promote self-directed learning among English teacher education students by providing strategies and resources for independent language exploration. Recommending useful websites, online platforms, mobile apps, and library resources helped students take ownership of their learning. Teachers were also advised to integrate assignments that required students to search for additional language resources independently. By fostering autonomy, students were more likely to develop deeper cognitive engagement with the subject.

Further, teachers should create opportunities for peer collaboration in the classroom. Group discussions, peer tutoring, and collaborative learning activities were advised to be integrated into the curriculum to allow students to support one another in understanding difficult language concepts. Teachers who fostered environments where students could exchange ideas and work together increased engagement and sustained students' interest in language learning. Structured group work and project-based learning were suggested to enhance both

teamwork skills and subject mastery.

In addition, teachers should offer personalized support to students facing challenges in language learning, particularly when dealing with unfamiliar vocabulary or complex topics. Frequent assessment of students' understanding, followed by tailored guidance, helped address individual difficulties. Teachers were encouraged to adopt flexible teaching strategies based on specific needs, ensuring that students remained confident and motivated. Providing additional tutorials or one-on-one sessions helped prevent struggling students from falling behind.

To add up, the integration of technology into language instruction should also be considered to increase student engagement. Teachers were encouraged to use language-learning apps, multimedia resources, and educational websites to make lessons more interactive and enjoyable. They were advised to utilize visual aids, online platforms, and gamified tools to present language concepts in engaging ways. By offering students opportunities to practice language skills through technology outside of the classroom, teachers extended learning time and improved language proficiency.

Also, teachers should incorporate real-world applications into their lessons to make language learning more relevant and meaningful. Project-based learning, where students applied language skills to real-life tasks, was found to enhance student engagement and show the practical benefits of language proficiency. Teachers who used examples from everyday life, professional communication, and media were able to demonstrate the value of language skills. Connecting theoretical concepts to real-world scenarios increased students' interest and motivation.

Additionally, teachers should foster both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation in students. This was achieved by helping students set personal learning goals and reminding them of the long-term benefits of language proficiency, such as career advancement and effective communication. Offering positive reinforcement and recognizing student achievements further enhanced motivation. Teachers who promoted a growth mindset encouraged students to view challenges as opportunities for growth rather than obstacles.

Consequently, teachers were encouraged to seek regular feedback from students regarding their learning experiences. By asking for input on teaching methods, lesson content, and areas where students needed additional support, teachers were able to adjust their instructional approaches to better meet student needs. Encouraging students to reflect on their progress and learning goals helped them remain engaged and motivated throughout their language learning journey.

Lastly, the results from the study emphasized the critical role of teacher effectiveness in influencing the language interest and engagement of English teacher education students. Teachers who promoted self-directed learning, facilitated peer collaboration, provided personalized support, and integrated technology into their instruction were found to have a profound impact on students' language interest. By connecting language learning to real-world applications and providing continuous encouragement, teachers played a key role in sustaining students' interest in mastering the English language. These findings suggest that teacher effectiveness is a vital factor in fostering a dynamic and supportive learning environment that promotes long-term student engagement and success in language education.

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